

Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Institute of Mathematics

Perturbation-based confidence regions and their application to stochastic bandits

Master's thesis

Botond Kiss

Supervisors:

Dr. Balázs Csanád Csáji

SZTAKI

Senior research fellow

Dr. Gábor Pete

BME Department of Stochastics

Associate professor

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Acknowledgements

The research in this thesis was supported by the Artificial Intelligence National Laboratory Program.

I owe a great debt of gratitude to Balázs Csanád Csáji for his invaluable guidance. I appreciate his insightful advice that I received during the preparation of this Master's thesis. I would also like to thank Gábor Pete for his useful suggestions, which contributed to improving the thesis.

Last but not least, I express my sincere gratitude to my family for their everlasting support and encouragement.

Introduction

Constructing confidence intervals via data perturbation can be used as a system identification approach to estimate the parameter of linear regression models. Such a method is called Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS), which is a novel, nonparametric solution that relies only on mild statistical assumptions and provides non-asymptotic confidence set that contains the unknown system parameter with predetermined probability. The essence of this thesis is the exhaustive analysis and machine learning application of the SPS method.

In the first chapter of the thesis, we give a brief insight into stochastic multi-armed bandit (MAB) problems, which are sequential decision making tasks in random environments. MAB problems illustrate the core dilemma of reinforcement learning (which is one of the three branches of machine learning), the exploration vs. exploitation dilemma. We give an overview of the key concepts of bandits and a state of the art approach, called Upper Confidence Bound policy, which is proven to be an efficient (but typically parametric) solution to tackle such stochastic sequential allocation problems.

In the second part, we get acquainted with Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS) method, and we present several known properties of SPS confidence regions regarding their shape and size. Furthermore, as our contribution to the existing theory of SPS, we examine the cases of degenerate confidence sets and estimate the probability of their occurrence. We also present a generalization of the SPS method, which allows not only sign but also symmetrical data perturbation, and prove the exact confidence level of the regions provided by symmetrically-perturbed sums method. In addition, we consider further modifications that do not affect the inclusion of the system parameter with the user-chosen confidence probability.

In general, the determination of SPS confidence regions in a compact representation is a computationally intensive task. However, in one dimension, the exact confidence region can be calculated efficiently in closed form. In the final, third chapter of the thesis, we examine the one-dimensional SPS method to gain deeper understanding of the construction. Using the alterations proved in the second chapter, we introduce the linear SPS method, which provides semi-infinite confidence intervals. Lastly, we propose a nonparametric, perturbation-based stochastic multi armed bandit algorithm (which relies on linear SPS). To empirically compare it with existing UCB policy, we implemented in Python all the algorithms to be examined in the thesis and ran various simulations.

Chapter 1

Stochastic Multi-armed Bandits

In reinforcement learning the multi-armed bandit (MAB) problem is a fundamental sequential decision making problem under uncertainty, where the decision maker (agent) interacts with an unknown or partially-known environment. In each round the agent chooses an action (bandit arm) from a finite set and feeds it into the environment. As response the environment gives feedback to the agent in form of a reward (random reward in case of stochastic bandits). The agent makes a decision in each round based on the history of rewards. The learning objective is to maximize the cumulative rewards. This particular decision making problem illustratively presents the core problem of reinforcement learning, the exploration-exploitation trade-off: whether to choose the best possible action at a given time or keep exploring seemingly sub-optimal actions.

The first known application of bandits was performed in clinical trials according to a paper published in 1933 [21]. Instead of dividing patients into groups, the treatments were applied sequentially (each person received only one kind of treatment), based on the previous results, whether or not the usage of a certain treatment has proven to be effective. Nowadays bandit algorithms are widely used in order to solve real life problems, e.g. advert placement optimization, dynamic pricing, recommendation systems, network routing, tree search in games like chess and go, etc.

1.1 Introduction to stochastic multi-armed bandits

In this section, we provide an overview of the key concepts of stochastic multi-armed bandits (MAB) based on the introductory Chapters of [15], [19] and [5].

Definition 1.1.1. Stochastic multi-armed bandit (MAB) environment is an indexed family of probability distributions $\nu = (P_a : a \in \mathcal{A})$, where \mathcal{A} is the finite set of actions (in other words, the arms of the bandit). If $|\nu| = k$, then the arms are indexed by $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, and ν is called a k -armed bandit.

Remark 1.1.1. If it is not stated otherwise, for a k -armed bandit the action set will

be considered as an index set $\mathcal{A} = \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$. Furthermore, when we talk about a multi-armed bandit we refer to the defining environment.

The horizon is the total number of rounds the sequential game is played, which is often not predetermined. It may be unknown for the decision maker, or it is infinite. In case of finite horizon, we denote it with n . We also use the notation $[n] = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ in general (e.g. $[k]$ for the arms of a bandit).

Now we discuss the mathematical formalization of the decision maker's interaction with the environment. The agent forms a control policy based on the history of actions and rewards $H_t = (A_1, X_1, A_2, X_2, \dots, A_t, X_t)$ in order to determine which arm to be chosen at time $t + 1$.

Definition 1.1.2. The control policy at time $t \in \mathbb{N}^+$ is a function π_t , that determines which action to take in the next round $t + 1$. Assuming that the stochastic rewards are real numbers

$$\pi_t : (\mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R})^t \rightarrow \mathcal{A} \quad (\text{deterministic case}), \quad (1.1)$$

$$\pi_t : (\mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{R})^t \rightarrow \Delta\mathcal{A} \quad (\text{randomized case}), \quad (1.2)$$

where $\Delta\mathcal{A}$ is the set of random variables that take values in \mathcal{A} . Control policy is a sequence $\pi = (\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots)$ if the horizon is infinite. When the horizon is finite, then $\pi = (\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_n)$.

The decision maker oftentimes has partial knowledge about the environment, which can be encapsulated in the form of a set that restricts the possible distributions of the bandit arms.

Definition 1.1.3. Let $\nu = (P_a : a \in \mathcal{A})$ be a stochastic multi-armed bandit. Then the set of stochastic multi-armed bandits \mathcal{E} is called environment class of ν if $\nu \in \mathcal{E}$.

For instance, the environment class of k -armed Gaussian bandits for known and unknown variance cases are defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{N}}^k = \{(\mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2))_{i=1}^k : \mu_i \in \mathbb{R}, \sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}^+\}, \quad (1.3)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{N}}^k(\sigma) = \{(\mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma^2))_{i=1}^k : \mu_i \in \mathbb{R}\}. \quad (1.4)$$

Definition 1.1.4. A multi-armed bandit environment class \mathcal{E} is called unstructured if $|\mathcal{A}| < \infty$ and for each $a \in \mathcal{A}$ exists a set of distributions \mathcal{P}_a such that

$$\mathcal{E} = \{\nu = (P_a : a \in \mathcal{A}) : \forall a \in \mathcal{A} P_a \in \mathcal{P}_a\}. \quad (1.5)$$

That is $\mathcal{E} = \times_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \mathcal{P}_a$. Furthermore, if \mathcal{E} is not unstructured, then it is called structured.

The Gaussian environment classes mentioned above are unstructured. Being unstructured means that by playing a given action the decision maker cannot receive information about other arms. On the other hand, structured bandits provide the opportunity to extract the information about the environment structure. For instance, if a two-armed Bernoulli bandit $\mathcal{E} = (\mathcal{B}(\theta), \mathcal{B}(1 - \theta))$ is given for some $\theta \in (1/2, 1)$, then choosing the first arm gives the optimal allocation strategy, and the parameter of both arms can be estimated simultaneously.

An efficient policy needs to utilize the information of the environment class and find a delicate balance between exploration and exploitation. A basic policy called explore-then-commit (ETC) separates these two sharply [15]. First, it simply chooses each and every action for fixed number of times $m > 0$ (i.e. exploration lasts for $k \cdot m$ rounds). After that it plays the best arm from the exploration phase in the remaining rounds (exploitation).

The general form of the interaction process is described in the following way:

Stochastic multi-armed bandit protocol

Input: action set \mathcal{A} , environment class \mathcal{E} .

For each round $t = 1, 2, \dots$

1. The decision maker chooses an arm $A_t = a_t \in \mathcal{A}$ and feeds it to the environment \mathcal{E} .
 2. The agent receives stochastic reward $X_t = x_{t,A_t} \in \mathbb{R}$, sampled by the environment, independently of previous rewards that correspond to arm a_t .
-

It is possible that the environment class is nonparametric, or totally unknown. In this case, the agent has to make a policy using little or no prior information on the distributions of the underlying bandit arms. The independence assumption, stated in the MAB protocol, implies that rewards, given by a certain arm, form a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variables (more precisely a realization of i.i.d. sequence).

In what follows, we define the goal of the decision making process by using the concept of regret. It helps to analyse the efficiency of the agent and can be used to compare different policies. The overall purpose of the sequential learning is to maximize the sum of rewards $\sum_{t=1}^n X_t$ up to time instance t . In the scholarly literature of bandit problems, the learning objective is typically considered to be regret minimization, which is closely related to cumulative reward maximization.

Definition 1.1.5. For a stochastic k -armed bandit ν ($k \geq 2$) the mean of an arm $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is the expectation of the corresponding distribution:

$$\mu_a(\nu) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x dP_a(x), \tag{1.6}$$

assuming that the integral exists and is finite (if the underlying bandit environment is unequivocal from the context, we simply denote the mean of an arm a by μ_a).

The highest expectation is denoted by $\mu^*(\nu) = \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \mu_a$, hence an optimal arm is $a^* \in \operatorname{argmax}_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \mu_a(\nu) \neq \emptyset$ (there may be more than one optimal arm).

Definition 1.1.6. Let ν be a stochastic k -armed bandit environment. The regret of a π policy in ν after n rounds is

$$R_n(\pi, \nu) = n\mu^*(\nu) - \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n X_t \right], \quad (1.7)$$

where X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n denote the first n rewards generated by the environment. A probability measure is induced on the rewards by π interacting with ν , thus the expectation is taken with respect to this particular probability measure.

Maximizing the expectation of the cumulative rewards (i.e. $\mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=1}^n X_t]$) is equivalent to minimizing regret. Furthermore, by the definition of μ^* , the regret is a nonnegative quantity. It equals to 0 if and only if π chooses an optimal arm in each round. If the policy and the underlying bandit environment is unequivocal from the context, we denote the regret by R_n . From now on, we will use the regret as the core tool for the theoretical analysis of the efficiency of bandit algorithms. The ultimate goal of every bandit policy construction is to achieve sublinear regret:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_n(\pi, \nu)}{n} = 0. \quad (1.8)$$

Finally, we present an alternative way to formulate regret by using the concept of suboptimality gaps.

Definition 1.1.7. In case of $\nu = (P_a : a \in \mathcal{A})$ k -armed bandit environment, the suboptimality gap (or immediate regret) of arm $a \in \mathcal{A}$ is defined as

$$\Delta_a(\nu) = \mu^*(\nu) - \mu_a(\nu). \quad (1.9)$$

Similarly as before, we omit ν from the notation and use Δ_a if the underlying bandit is irrelevant or clear from the context. In addition, let the number of times a certain action was chosen by the decision maker after t rounds be denoted by

$$T_a(t) = \sum_{s=1}^t \mathbb{I}\{A_s = a\}. \quad (1.10)$$

Using the introduced notations we can give the following equivalent form of the regret.

Lemma 1.1.1 (Regret decomposition lemma). *Let $\nu = (P_a : a \in \mathcal{A})$ be a stochastic multi-armed bandit with countable action set. Then the regret of any π policy in ν is*

$$R_n(\pi, \nu) = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \Delta_a \mathbb{E} [T_a(n)], \quad (1.11)$$

where n is the finite horizon.

Proof. For a fixed $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ $\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} = 1$, since in round t exactly one action was played. Thus

$$\sum_{t=1}^n X_t = \sum_{t=1}^n X_t \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} = \sum_{t=1}^n \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} X_t \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} \quad (1.12)$$

Based on this, we can write the regret in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} R_n &= n\mu^* - \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n X_t \right] = n\mu^* - \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} X_t \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} \right] = \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t=1}^n \mathbb{E} [(\mu^* - X_t) \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\}] \\ &= \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t=1}^n \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbb{E} [(\mu^* - X_t) \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} | A_t] \right], \end{aligned} \quad (1.13)$$

where in the last equation we applied the tower rule. Now let's transform the inner expectation.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} [(\mu^* - X_t) \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} | A_t] &= \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} \mathbb{E} [\mu^* - X_t | A_t] = \\ &= \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} \left(\mathbb{E} [\mu^* | A_t] - \mathbb{E} [X_t | A_t] \right) = \\ &= \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} (\mu^* - \mu_{A_t}) = \\ &= \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} (\mu^* - \mu_a) = \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} \Delta_a \end{aligned} \quad (1.14)$$

In calculation (1.14) the following facts were used in order: $\mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\}$ is the function of A_t , the linearity of conditional expectation, μ^* is constant, and the reward at time t conditioned on A_t is exactly μ_{A_t} ($\mathbb{E} [X_t | A_t] = \mu_{A_t}$). Due to the fact that $\mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} = 0$ implies $\mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} (\mu^* - \mu_{A_t}) = 0$, the penultimate equation holds. Finally we use the definition of suboptimality gap. Hence by applying (1.14) substitution to (1.13) we get the desired result:

$$R_n = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t=1}^n \mathbb{E} [\mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} \Delta_a] = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \Delta_a \mathbb{E} \sum_{t=1}^n \mathbb{I}\{A_t = a\} = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \Delta_a \mathbb{E} [T_a(n)]. \quad (1.15)$$

□

1.2 Subgaussian random variables

In this section, we review important concentration inequalities, which are to be used in MAB policy planning in the later parts of this chapter (for reference see Chapter 2 of [22], concentration of measure section of [15], Chapter 2 of [4], and [18]).

Definition 1.2.1. An X random variable is called σ -subgaussian if for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ the following upper bound holds for its moment generating function:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[e^{\lambda X} \right] \leq e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2}. \quad (1.16)$$

σ is called subgaussian constant of X .

One can give meaning to the subgaussian appellation by observing that the moment-generating function of a standard normal random variable $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is $M_Z(\lambda) = e^{\frac{\lambda^2}{2}}$. Consequently, for a zero mean Gaussian random variable $X = \sigma Z$ we have $M_X(\lambda) = e^{\frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \lambda^2}$, i.e. any zero mean Gaussian random variable satisfies the defining inequality of subgaussian random variables with equality.

Definition 1.2.2. Let X be a real-valued random variable provided that its expectation exists. Then for $\varepsilon > 0$ the lower tail probability of X is $\mathbb{P}(X - \mathbb{E}[X] \leq -\varepsilon)$, and the upper tail probability of X is $\mathbb{P}(X - \mathbb{E}[X] \geq \varepsilon)$. Both considered as functions of ε . Furthermore, $\mathbb{P}(|X - \mathbb{E}[X]| \geq \varepsilon)$ is called two-sided tail probability.

From now on, we examine the tail probabilities of subgaussian random variables. We will use the so-called Cramér–Chernoff method to prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1.2.1. *If X is σ -subgaussian random variable, then $\forall \varepsilon \geq 0$*

$$\mathbb{P}(X \geq \varepsilon) \leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\sigma^2}}. \quad (1.17)$$

Proof. Let $\lambda > 0$ be a constant whose exact value is to be determined later. Then using Markov's inequality and the definition of subgaussian random variables we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(X \geq \varepsilon) &= \mathbb{P}(\lambda X \geq \lambda \varepsilon) = \mathbb{P}\left(e^{\lambda X} \geq e^{\lambda \varepsilon}\right) \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[e^{\lambda X}]}{e^{\lambda \varepsilon}} = \mathbb{E}\left[e^{\lambda X}\right] e^{-\lambda \varepsilon} \leq \\ &\leq e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2} e^{-\lambda \varepsilon} = e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2 - \lambda \varepsilon} \doteq \psi(\lambda). \end{aligned} \quad (1.18)$$

We are looking for the minimum of $\psi(\lambda) : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ in λ .

$$\psi'(\lambda) = (\lambda \sigma^2 - \varepsilon) e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2 - \lambda \varepsilon} \quad (1.19)$$

$$\psi''(\lambda) = \sigma^2 e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2 - \lambda \varepsilon} + (\lambda \sigma^2 - \varepsilon)^2 e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2 - \lambda \varepsilon} > 0, \quad (1.20)$$

hence ψ is convex, and local minimum of ψ in λ is taken when

$$\frac{d}{d\lambda}\psi(\lambda) = 0 \iff \lambda = \varepsilon/\sigma^2 > 0. \quad (1.21)$$

Since $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \psi(\lambda) = \infty$, $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \psi(\lambda) = 1$, and $\psi(\varepsilon/\sigma^2) = e^{-\varepsilon^2/(2\sigma^2)} \leq 1$, we can conclude that in $\lambda = \varepsilon/\sigma^2$ the function $\psi(\lambda)$ takes its global minimum. All in all, we get

$$\mathbb{P}(X \geq \varepsilon) \leq e^{\frac{1}{2}\lambda^2\sigma^2 - \lambda\varepsilon} \Big|_{\lambda=\varepsilon/\sigma^2} = e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\sigma^2}}. \quad (1.22)$$

□

Remark 1.2.1. By simply applying Theorem 1.2.1 to $-X$ one can obtain the same bound for lower tails. Furthermore, by using union bound, the estimations of lower and upper tails imply the two-sided tail bound.

$$\mathbb{P}(X \leq -\varepsilon) \leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (\text{lower-tail}) \quad (1.23)$$

$$\mathbb{P}(|X| \geq \varepsilon) \leq 2e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (\text{two-sided tail}) \quad (1.24)$$

Remark 1.2.2. We referred to (1.17), (1.23) and (1.24) as tail probabilities even though they differ from the definition of tails 1.2.2. This apparent contradiction can be resolved by the fact that every subgaussian random variable has zero expectation, which is to be proven soon.

In conclusion, the tail probability of any σ -subgaussian random variable decays at least as fast as a zero mean Gaussian's tail whose standard deviation is σ . By these bounds one-sided and two-sided confidence sets can be derived. Let $\delta \doteq 2e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\sigma^2}}$ (such that $\delta \in (0, 1)$). Then

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\delta/2) &= -\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2\sigma^2} \\ -2\sigma^2 \log(\delta/2) &= \varepsilon^2 \\ \sqrt{2\sigma^2 \log(2/\delta)} &= \varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (1.25)$$

Thus for a σ -subgaussian variable X we have

$$\mathbb{P}(|X| \geq \varepsilon) = \mathbb{P}\left(|X| \geq \sqrt{2\sigma^2 \log(2/\delta)}\right) \leq \delta, \quad (1.26)$$

which yields an $1 - \delta$ level confidence set for X :

$$\left(-\sqrt{2\sigma^2 \log(2/\delta)}, \sqrt{2\sigma^2 \log(2/\delta)}\right). \quad (1.27)$$

From now on, we would like to examine sequences subgaussian random variables,

and the goal is to construct tail bounds for sample means. The following propositions yield useful properties of subgaussian random variables regarding their expected value and scalability. For reference see Subnormal Distribution section in Chapter 9 of book [20], and Chapter 1 of [6].

Lemma 1.2.2. *Let X be a σ -subgaussian random variable. Then*

$$(i) \mathbb{E}[X] = 0, \text{Var}[X] \leq \sigma^2.$$

$$(ii) \forall c \in \mathbb{R} \ cX \text{ is } |c|\sigma\text{-subgaussian}$$

Proof. (i) Let $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ be an arbitrary, fixed number. By the Taylor expansion of the exponential function we get

$$e^{\lambda X} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} X^k \doteq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varphi_n(X), \quad (1.28)$$

thus $\varphi_n(X)$ converges pointwise to $e^{\lambda X}$. Furthermore, the absolute value of $\varphi_n(X)$ can be dominated by $g(X) = e^{\lambda X} + e^{-\lambda X}$ in the following manner:

$$\begin{aligned} |\varphi_n| &= \left| \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} X^k \right| \leq \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{|\lambda X|^k}{k!} \leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{|\lambda X|^k}{k!} = e^{|\lambda X|} \leq \\ &\leq e^{\lambda X} + e^{-\lambda X} = g(X), \end{aligned} \quad (1.29)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[g(X)] \leq 2e^{\frac{1}{2}\lambda^2\sigma^2}$ by subgaussian property of X . Therefore, Lebesgue's dominated convergence theorem (see section 1.3 of [12]) is applicable:

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{\lambda X}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varphi_n(X)\right] = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\varphi_n(X)] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} \mathbb{E}[X^k] \quad (1.30)$$

Using subgaussian property and Taylor expansion one more time:

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{\lambda X}] \leq e^{\frac{1}{2}\lambda^2\sigma^2} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\frac{1}{2}\lambda^2\sigma^2)^k}{k!} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{2k}\sigma^{2k}}{2^k k!} \quad (1.31)$$

Putting (1.30) and (1.31) together:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \lambda \mathbb{E}[X] + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \mathbb{E}[X^2] + \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} \mathbb{E}[X^k] &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} \mathbb{E}[X^k] = \\ &= \mathbb{E}[e^{\lambda X}] \leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{2k}\sigma^{2k}}{2^k k!} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}\lambda^2\sigma^2 + \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{2k}\sigma^{2k}}{2^k k!}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.32)$$

hence

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda \mathbb{E}[X] + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \mathbb{E}[X^2] &\leq \frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2 + \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda^{2k} \sigma^{2k}}{2^k k!} - \frac{\lambda^k}{k!} \mathbb{E}[X^k] \right) \\ \lambda \mathbb{E}[X] + \frac{\lambda^2}{2} \mathbb{E}[X^2] &\leq \frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma^2 + f(\lambda),\end{aligned}\tag{1.33}$$

where $f \in o(\lambda^2)$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ (namely $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} f(\lambda)/\lambda^2 = 0$), and f contains all the elements from the two Taylor expansions (rearranged to the right hand side in the inequality (1.33)) that have terms of order greater than 2 in λ . Finally, let's analyze inequality (1.33). Assuming that $\lambda > 0$, dividing both sides by λ and taking limit as $\lambda \rightarrow 0_+$ we get $\mathbb{E}[X] \leq 0$ (by Taylor expansion (1.31) $f(\lambda)$ nonnegative function is polynomial in λ , and can be written as $f(\lambda) = \lambda^3 h(\lambda)$, which means that $f \in o(\lambda)$ as $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ holds too). Similarly, when $\lambda < 0$, taking limit as $\lambda \rightarrow 0_-$ we get $\mathbb{E}[X] \geq 0$, which concludes that $\mathbb{E}[X] = 0$. Furthermore, if we divide both sides by $\lambda^2 > 0$ and take limit as λ goes to 0, then

$$\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\mathbb{E}[X]}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}[X^2] \right) \leq \frac{\sigma^2}{2} + \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(\lambda)}{\lambda^2},\tag{1.34}$$

thus

$$\text{Var}[X] = \mathbb{E}[X^2] \leq \sigma^2,\tag{1.35}$$

where we used that $\mathbb{E}[X] = 0$.

- (ii) Let $c \in \mathbb{R}$ be an arbitrary, fixed number. Provided that X is σ -subgaussian and $\lambda \cdot c \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$M_{cX}(\lambda) = \mathbb{E}\left[e^{\lambda(cX)}\right] = \mathbb{E}\left[e^{(\lambda c)X}\right] \leq e^{\frac{(\lambda c)^2 \sigma^2}{2}} = e^{\frac{\lambda^2 (c\sigma)^2}{2}}.\tag{1.36}$$

Thus cX is $\sqrt{c^2 \sigma^2} = |c| \sigma$ -subgaussian. □

Lemma 1.2.3. *Let $(X_i)_{i=1}^n$ be an independent, σ_i -subgaussian sample ($i \in [n]$ $\sigma_i > 0$). Then*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n X_i \text{ is } \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}\text{-subgaussian.}\tag{1.37}$$

Proof. Due to independence, for any $s > 0$

$$\mathbb{E}\left[e^{\lambda \sum_{i=1}^n X_i}\right] = \mathbb{E}\left[\prod_{i=1}^n e^{\lambda X_i}\right] = \prod_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}\left[e^{\lambda X_i}\right] \leq \prod_{i=1}^n e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sigma_i^2} = e^{\frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}.\tag{1.38}$$

Consequently, by definition 1.2.1, the sum of n independent σ_i -subgaussian variables ($i \in [n]$) is exactly $\sqrt{\sum_i^n \sigma_i^2}$ -subgaussian. \square

By now, we have obtained all the knowledge that is required to examine tail probabilities of subgaussian samples as consequence of Lemma 1.2.2, Lemma 1.2.3 and Theorem 1.2.1.

Lemma 1.2.4. *For $i \in [n]$ let X_i be random variable with $\mathbb{E}[X_i] = \mu_i$. Assume that $X_i - \mu_i$ is σ_i -subgaussian, and denote the sample mean by $\hat{\mu} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$. Then*

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\hat{\mu} \geq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i + \varepsilon \right) \leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}} \quad (\text{upper tail}) \quad (1.39)$$

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\hat{\mu} \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i - \varepsilon \right) \leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}} \quad (\text{lower tail}) \quad (1.40)$$

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\left| \hat{\mu} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \right| \geq \varepsilon \right) \leq 2e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}} \quad (\text{two-sided tail}) \quad (1.41)$$

Proof. We prove only the upper tail estimate. Lower tail bound can be derived from the upper tail bound by applying it to $-X_1, \dots, -X_n$ sample. By Lemma 1.2.2 and 1.2.3, we know that $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \mu_i)$ is $\frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}$ -subgaussian. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P} \left(\hat{\mu} \geq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i + \varepsilon \right) &= \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \geq \varepsilon \right) \\ &= \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \mu_i) \geq \varepsilon \right) \leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.42)$$

Moreover, the two-sided tail probability estimate can be obtained by applying the union bound to the following union of two events:

$$\left\{ \left| \hat{\mu} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \right| \geq \varepsilon \right\} = \left\{ \hat{\mu} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \leq -\varepsilon \right\} \cup \left\{ \hat{\mu} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \geq \varepsilon \right\}. \quad (1.43)$$

\square

Remark 1.2.3. In case of a random variable X , that is not centered around 0 (i.e. $\mathbb{E}[X] \neq 0$), we say that it is σ -subgaussian if the noise defined by $X - \mathbb{E}[X]$ is σ -subgaussian.

Assume that $\mathbb{E}[X_i] = \mu$ for all $i \in [n]$. Similarly as for a single random variable, we can construct confidence intervals for the mean of a subgaussian sample. Restricting

$\delta \in (0, 1)$,

$$\begin{aligned}\delta &= 2e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}} \\ \log(2/\delta) &= \frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2} \\ \sqrt{\frac{2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2 \right) \log(2/\delta)}{n^2}} &= \varepsilon.\end{aligned}\tag{1.44}$$

Then the two-sided tail probability bound from Lemma 1.2.4 can be written as

$$\mathbb{P} \left(|\hat{\mu} - \mu| \geq \sqrt{\frac{2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2 \right) \log(2/\delta)}{n^2}} \right) \leq \delta,\tag{1.45}$$

which provides the following at least $1 - \delta$ level confidence set for the mean of our subgaussian sample:

$$\mu \in \left(\hat{\mu} - \sqrt{\frac{2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2 \right) \log(2/\delta)}{n^2}}, \hat{\mu} + \sqrt{\frac{2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2 \right) \log(2/\delta)}{n^2}} \right).\tag{1.46}$$

Remark 1.2.4. One can give one-sided confidence set for the expected value of a sample $(X_i)_{i=1}^n$, where X_i is σ_i -subgaussian and $\mathbb{E}[X_i] = \mu$:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\hat{\mu} + \sqrt{\frac{2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2 \right) \log(1/\delta)}{n^2}} \geq \mu \right) \geq 1 - \delta,\tag{1.47}$$

where $\delta \in (0, 1)$, $\delta = e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^2}}$.

Remark 1.2.5. From now on, due to readability reasons, when we talk about subgaussian samples we always refer to sequence of random variables with 1-subgaussian noise (i.e. $X_i - \mu_i$ is 1-subgaussian) if not stated otherwise. It can be done without loss of generality due to scaling property (second proposition in Lemma 1.2.2) and Lemma 1.2.3.

In the final part of this section, we examine the connection between subgaussian and bounded samples.

Lemma 1.2.5 (Hoeffding's lemma). *Let X be a random variable such that $\mathbb{E}[X] = 0$. Furthermore, let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ be two constants for which $a \leq X \leq b$ holds almost surely. Then for all $s > 0$*

$$\mathbb{E} \left[e^{sX} \right] \leq e^{\frac{s^2(b-a)^2}{8}}.\tag{1.48}$$

Proof. If $a = b$, then $X = 0$ almost surely, and the inequality holds trivially. From now

on, assume that $a \neq b$. Using the facts that $X \in [a, b]$ with probability one, $\mathbb{E}[X] = 0$, and exploiting convexity of the exponential function we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[e^{sX} \right] &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{X-a}{b-a} e^{sb} + \frac{b-X}{b-a} e^{sa} \right] = e^{sb} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{X-a}{b-a} \right] + e^{sa} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{b-X}{b-a} \right] = \\ &= -\frac{a}{b-a} e^{bs} + \frac{b}{b-a} e^{sa}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.49)$$

Let $p = -a/(b-a)$, then $b = a(p-1)/p$, thus

$$\frac{b}{b-a} = \frac{\frac{1}{p}(p-1)a}{\frac{1}{p}(p-1)a - a} = \frac{(p-1)}{(p-1) - p} = 1 - p. \quad (1.50)$$

Using this and the fact that from the definition of p we can express $a = -(b-a)p$, the inequality (1.49) can be reformulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[e^{sX} \right] &\leq p e^{bs} + (1-p) e^{sa} = p e^{bs} + (1-p) e^{-ps(b-a)} \\ &= \left(\frac{p e^{bs}}{e^{-ps(b-a)}} + 1 - p \right) e^{-ps(b-a)} = (p e^{bs+ps(b-a)} + 1 - p) e^{-ps(b-a)} = \\ &= \left(p e^{bs+\frac{-a}{b-a}s(b-a)} + 1 - p \right) e^{-ps(b-a)} = (p e^{s(b-a)+1-p}) e^{-ps(b-a)}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.51)$$

Now let's define $u = s(b-a)$ and $\phi(u) = -pu + \log(1-p + p e^u)$. It is clear that

$$e^{\phi(u)} = (p e^{s(b-a)+1-p}) e^{-ps(b-a)}, \quad (1.52)$$

which is exactly what we have got in (1.51). In the next step, we examine the derivatives of the function ϕ :

$$\phi'(u) = -p + \frac{p}{p + (1-p) e^{-u}}. \quad (1.53)$$

$$\phi''(u) = \frac{p(1-p) e^{-u}}{(p + (1-p) e^{-u})^2}. \quad (1.54)$$

We can conclude that $\phi(0) = \phi'(0) = 0$. Furthermore, by the inequality of arithmetic and geometric means (for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$ $\sqrt{xy} \leq (x+y)/2 \implies (xy)/(x+y)^2 \leq 1/4$) we get that $\phi''(u) \leq 1/4$ for every $u \in \mathbb{R}$. By Taylor's theorem, $\exists \xi \in (0, u)$ such that

$$\phi(u) = \phi(0) + \phi'(0)u + \phi''(\xi) \frac{u^2}{2} \leq \frac{u^2}{8} = \frac{s^2(b-a)^2}{8}. \quad (1.55)$$

□

Corollary 1.2.6 (Hoeffding's inequality). *Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be independent, bounded random variables, i.e. $\forall i \in [n] \exists a_i, b_i : X_i \in [a_i, b_i]$ almost surely. Furthermore, assume*

that $\exists i \in [n]$ ($a_i \neq b_i$). Then for all $\varepsilon > 0$

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right] \geq \varepsilon \right) \leq e^{-\frac{2\varepsilon^2 n^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i - a_i)^2}} \quad (1.56)$$

Proof. By Hoeffding's Lemma 1.2.5 we get that $X_i - \mathbb{E}[X_i]$ is $\sqrt{\frac{(b_i - a_i)^2}{4}}$ -subgaussian. So the sample mean $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \mathbb{E}[X_i])$ is $\frac{1}{n} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(b_i - a_i)^2}{4}}$ -subgaussian (see Lemma 1.2.3 and Lemma 1.2.2). According to 1.2.4, we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right] \geq \varepsilon \right) &= \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \mathbb{E}[X_i]) \geq \varepsilon \right) \\ &\leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(b_i - a_i)^2}{4}}} = e^{-\frac{2\varepsilon^2 n^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i - a_i)^2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.57)$$

□

Remark 1.2.6. The technical assumption that there exists $i \in [n]$ such that $a_i \neq b_i$ is required to avoid 0 in the denominator. On the other hand, if every X_i was constant almost surely, then the event that the average of the centered variables $X_i - \mathbb{E}[X_i]$ is greater than some positive ε would be empty.

Remark 1.2.7. Hoeffding's inequality can be formulated for lower tail probabilities and two-sided tail probabilities similarly as in the general subgaussian case:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right] \leq -\varepsilon \right) \leq e^{-\frac{2\varepsilon^2 n^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i - a_i)^2}} \quad (\text{lower-tail}) \quad (1.58)$$

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\left| \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i - \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \right] \right| \geq \varepsilon \right) \leq 2e^{-\frac{2\varepsilon^2 n^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (b_i - a_i)^2}} \quad (\text{two-sided tail}) \quad (1.59)$$

1.3 Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) policies

Upper confidence bound (UCB) policies are effective and well-known approaches to tackle multi-armed bandit problems. Their core idea is the principle of optimism in the face of uncertainty [15], [5]. The concept means that such policy aims to find well-balanced trade-off between exploration and exploitation by making decision in every single round assuming that the environment acts as nice as potentially possible. In particular, the optimism principle in multi-armed bandit problems means that we assign a one-sided confidence interval to each arm based on previously observed evidence (data), which gives an upper estimate of the unknown mean of the arm with high

probability. After that, the agent forms a policy that chooses the arm with the highest confidence bound at the given time. As the number of observations from a given arm increases, its corresponding upper confidence bound "shrinks" (i.e. approximates the real mean parameter from above). The prime benefit of applying these kind of policies is that they do not rely on the knowledge of suboptimality gaps, and they can be set to be independent of the horizon.

The first upper confidence bound algorithm was introduced by Auer et al. [1]. They proposed a horizon independent multi-armed bandit policy for environment class of bounded bandits, which achieves sublinear regret. First we review a general approach to upper confidence bound policies based on the introductory part of [13] and Chapter 7 of [15]. Then, we present two algorithms for specific environment classes: the original UCB1 algorithm that uses Hoeffding's inequality, and a more general version for subgaussian environments.

In what follows, we examine $\nu = (P_a : a \in \mathcal{A})$ stochastic multi-armed bandits, for which $\mathcal{A} = \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, where $k \geq 2$. UCB1 and the subgaussian UCB algorithms, which we intend to review, are defined for certain environment classes, hence consider the following notations:

$$\mathcal{E}_{SG}^k(\sigma) = \{(P_a)_{a \in \mathcal{A}} : \forall a \in \mathcal{A} P_a \text{ is } \sigma\text{-subgaussian}\}, \quad (1.60)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{[a,b]}^k = \{(P_a)_{a \in \mathcal{A}} : \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \text{ supp}(P_a) \subseteq [a, b]\}. \quad (1.61)$$

Recall that within the realm of subgaussian bandits we will work with 1-subgaussian random variables (as well as environments) if not stated otherwise, and we say that $\nu \in \mathcal{E}_{SG}(1)$, if for every X reward, sampled by the ν environment, the noise $X - \mathbb{E}[X]$ is 1-subgaussian.

Let $(X_t)_{t=1}^n$ denote the sequence of all the rewards (regardless of the sampling arm) provided by the environment ν over n rounds. Then for $0 < t \leq n$

$$\hat{\mu}_i(t) = \frac{1}{T_i(t)} \sum_{s=1}^t \mathbb{I}\{A_s = i\} X_s \quad (1.62)$$

is the empirical mean of the rewards from arm $i \in \mathcal{A} = [k]$. Recall that $T_i(t) = \sum_{s=1}^t \mathbb{I}\{A_s = i\}$.

In what follows, we give an overview of a generic approach to UCB based policies. The core idea is to build a one-sided confidence interval around sample mean. Consider the rewards $(T_i(n) = n_i$ long sequence of random variables) from a single arm indexed by $i \in [k]$. Then for the real valued, independent, and identically distributed sample $(X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}$, $\mathcal{G}_i((X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}, 1 - \delta)$ is an at least $1 - \delta$ level confidence set for $\mu_i = \mathbb{E}[X_{i,t}]$ if

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\mu \in \mathcal{G}\left((X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}, 1 - \delta\right)\right) \geq 1 - \delta, \quad (1.63)$$

assuming that $\delta \in (0, 1)$. This confidence set can be defined by a semi-infinite confidence interval, namely

$$\mathcal{G}_i((X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}, 1 - \delta) = \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}, x - \hat{\mu}_i(n) \leq h_\delta((X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}) \right\}, \quad (1.64)$$

so it is built around the unbiased estimation of the expectation, i.e. the sample mean. $h_\delta((X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i})$ is typically obtained by tail probability estimation. A generic UCB algorithm would assign an upper confidence bound to each arm using the available independent and identically distributed rewards sampled by corresponding arm. Since the learning objective is the minimization of regret, equivalently maximization of cumulative rewards, the agent aims to find the arm with highest possible yield, thus a UCB algorithm should choose the action with the largest upper confidence bound $\hat{\mu}_i(n) + h_\delta((X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i})$ (where $i \in [k]$) at a given time. The upper bound of the semi-infinite confidence set corresponding to an arm is called the index of that particular arm.

1.3.1 UCB1 algorithm

From a historical point of view, UCB1 was the first bandit algorithm that used upper confidence bounds as optimistic estimators of the expected values of bandit arms [1]. It was originally proposed for bounded bandits with support in $[0, 1]$ (namely $\nu \in \mathcal{E}_{[0,1]}^k$) using Hoeffding's inequality, but it can be relaxed to arbitrary bounded support. Here we present the original version.

Let $(X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}$ be independent, identically distributed random variables, such that $\text{supp}(X_{i,t}) = [0, 1]$ for $t \in [n_i]$. We can consider $(X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}$ as the reward sequence of a bandit arm, where $T_i(n) = n_i$. Therefore, from inequality (1.58)

$$1 - \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{t=1}^{n_i} (X_{i,t} - \mu_i) \leq -\varepsilon\right) = \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{t=1}^{n_i} (X_{i,t} - \mu_i) \geq -\varepsilon\right) \leq 1 - e^{-\frac{2\varepsilon^2 n_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_i} (b_i - a_i)^2}}, \quad (1.65)$$

hence

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\mu_i \leq \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{t=1}^{n_i} X_{i,t} + \varepsilon\right) \leq 1 - e^{-\frac{2n_i^2 \varepsilon^2}{n_i}} = 1 - e^{-2n_i \varepsilon^2}. \quad (1.66)$$

By the choice of $\delta = e^{-2n_i \varepsilon^2}$ we have $\varepsilon = \sqrt{\frac{\log(1/\delta)}{2n_i}}$. The index of arm i after $t-1$ rounds is defined as

$$\text{UCB1}_i(t-1, \delta) = \begin{cases} \infty & , \text{ if } T_i(t-1) = 0 \\ \hat{\mu}_i(t-1) + \sqrt{\frac{\log(1/\delta)}{2T_i(t-1)}} & , \text{ if } T_i(t-1) \neq 0. \end{cases} \quad (1.67)$$

A generic upper confidence bound algorithm chooses an arm with the highest index (there may be more than one optimal arm). Setting every index to ∞ in case of $T_i(t-1) = 0$ is equivalent to playing each arm once during the first k rounds (for $\delta \in (0, 1)$ the bounded support assumption guarantees that after observing one reward from arm i the i^{th} index cannot be infinite a.s.). Note that in (1.67) the sample size is defined by a stopping time $T_i(t-1)$, even so Hoeffding's inequality was proven for fixed sample size. This technicality can be resolved in the way that Hoeffding's inequality remains applicable in the proof of the sublinearity of UCB1 policy's regret [1]. Furthermore, $1 - \delta$ confidence level may not be constant in time. If that so, we use the notation $\delta(t)$.

Algorithm 1 UCB1

Input: $\mathcal{A} = [k]$ action set, $\delta(t) : \mathbb{N}^+ \rightarrow (0, 1)$ function,
 For each round $t = 1, 2, \dots$

- Choose $A_t = \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in [k]} \text{UCB1}_i(t-1, \delta(t))$.
-

The UCB1 algorithm is anytime, which means that it does not depend on the horizon. However, there exists upper confidence bound policy versions that rely on the knowledge of the exact horizon (see subgaussian UCB in Chapter 7 in [15]). Choosing confidence level, namely determining δ is a non-trivial problem. Auer et al. [1] proved sublinear regret of UCB1 using $\delta(t) = t^{-4}$. Therefore, the index of arm i after $t > k$ rounds becomes

$$\hat{\mu}_i(t) + \sqrt{\frac{2 \log(t)}{T_i(t)}}. \quad (1.68)$$

Theorem 1.3.1. *In case of $\mathcal{E}_{[0,1]}^k$ bandit environment, the regret of UCB1 policy after n rounds can be bounded in the following way:*

$$R_n \leq \left\lceil 8 \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \frac{\log n}{\Delta_i} \right\rceil + \left(1 + \frac{\pi^2}{3}\right) \sum_{i=1}^k \Delta_i. \quad (1.69)$$

The proof of this theorem [1] is built on the decomposition of regret 1.11. The fundamental part of the regret analysis is the task of bounding $T_i(t)$ for each suboptimal arm. The achieved regret bound is clearly sublinear, but due to the fact that the reciprocals of the suboptimality gaps appear as constant multiplier factors of $\log(n)$, this bound may not be a meaningful estimate for certain bandit instances. These kind of regret bounds are called gap dependent bounds.

Remark 1.3.1. The summand $\sum_{i=1}^k \Delta_i$ is inevitable in any unstructured k -armed bandit algorithm's regret bound (that is sublinear) since the agent cannot find the optimal arm

(hence cannot minimize the regret) without playing each arm at least once.

We continue with the presentation of an improved argument, that leads to a more general sequential allocation policy.

1.3.2 Asymptotically Optimal UCB

In this subsection, we work with 1-subgaussian multi-armed bandits, i.e. $\nu \in \mathcal{E}_{\text{SG}}^k(1)$. We will show how an upper confidence bound policy, similar to UCB1, can be constructed using subgaussian tail bounds. The analysis of the algorithm presented here can be found in Chapter 8 and 16 of [15].

Assume that $(X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}$ is an independent and identically distributed sequence of 1-subgaussian random variables with $\mathbb{E}[X_{i,t}] = \mu_i < \infty$ (e.g. sampled by a stochastic MAB arm indexed by i). Recall that if $\mu_i \neq 0$, then the subgaussian assumption means that $X_{i,t} - \mu_i$ is 1-subgaussian. By Lemma 1.2.4, the lower tail probability bound of $\hat{\mu}_i = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{t=1}^{n_i} X_{i,t}$ becomes

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}_i \leq \mu_i - \varepsilon) \leq e^{-\frac{\varepsilon^2}{\frac{2}{n_i} \sum_{i=1}^{n_i} \sigma_i^2}} = e^{-\frac{n_i \varepsilon^2}{2}}. \quad (1.70)$$

By the choice of $\delta = e^{-\frac{1}{2}n_i\varepsilon^2}$ ($\delta \in (0, 1)$), we have $\varepsilon = \sqrt{\frac{2\log(1/\delta)}{n_i}}$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}_i \leq \mu_i - \varepsilon) &= \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}_i \geq \mu_i - \varepsilon) = \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mu}_i + \varepsilon \geq \mu_i) \geq 1 - \delta, \\ \mathbb{P}\left(\mu_i \leq \hat{\mu}_i + \sqrt{\frac{2\log(1/\delta)}{n_i}}\right) &\geq 1 - \delta, \end{aligned} \quad (1.71)$$

which provides an at least $1 - \delta$ level, one-sided confidence interval for the expected value of the sample $(X_{i,t})_{t=1}^{n_i}$. A subgaussian UCB policy creates $1 - \delta$ level upper bounds like (1.71) for each arm using the corresponding independent and identically distributed sequence of rewards (note that the technical issue of interchangeability of integer $n_i > 0$ and stopping time $T_i(t-1)$ occurs here as well).

Asymptotically optimal upper confidence bound algorithm 2 is also an anytime policy. It uses monotone increasing confidence level defined by the function $f(t) = 1 + t \log^2(t)$. At round t the level is $1 - 1/f(t)$, thus $\delta(t) = 1/f(t)$. Due to the subgaussian environment assumption, and by the aforementioned choice of $\delta(t)$, the agent can increase the confidence level of every arm's upper bound without sampling new rewards.

The regret analysis of Algorithm 2 leads to the following sublinear upper bound (for reference, see Chapter 8 of [15]):

Theorem 1.3.2. *Consider any stochastic k -armed bandit environment in $\mathcal{E}_{\text{SG}}^k(1)$. The*

Algorithm 2 Asymptotically optimal UCB

Input: action set $\mathcal{A} = [k]$.

1. Initializing: for $t = 1, 2, \dots, k$ choose $A_t = t$.
2. For $t = k + 1, k + 2, \dots$

- Choose $A_t = \operatorname{argmax}_{i \in \{1, \dots, k\}} \left(\hat{\mu}(t-1) + \sqrt{\frac{2 \log f(t)}{T_i(t-1)}} \right)$,
where $f(t) = 1 + t \log^2(t)$.

regret of the policy, induced by Algorithm 2, in ν can be bounded in the following way:

$$R_n \leq \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \inf_{\varepsilon \in (0, \Delta_i)} \Delta_i \left(1 + \frac{5}{\varepsilon^2} + \frac{2 \left(\log f(n) + \sqrt{\pi \log f(n) + 1} \right)}{(\Delta_i - \varepsilon)^2} \right). \quad (1.72)$$

Furthermore,

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_n}{\log n} \leq \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \frac{2}{\Delta_i} \quad (1.73)$$

In what follows, we briefly explain what asymptotical optimality means in this case (for reference, see Chapter 16 of [15]). First define the consistency of a policy:

Definition 1.3.1. A policy π is called consistent over \mathcal{E} environment class if $\forall \nu \in \mathcal{E} \forall p > 0$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_n(\pi, \nu)}{n^p} = 0. \quad (1.74)$$

Set of consistent policies over \mathcal{E} is denoted by $\Pi_{\text{cons}}(\mathcal{E})$.

For instance, the policy that corresponds to Algorithm 2 is consistent over $\mathcal{E}_{[0,1]}^k$ for any $k > 0$ due to fact that the derived regret bound $R_n = O(\log n)$ by Theorem 1.3.1 (recall that $f(x) = O(g(x))$ if $\exists M \in \mathbb{R}^+ \exists x_0 \in \mathbb{R} : \forall x \geq x_0 |f(x)| \leq M|g(x)|$).

Definition 1.3.2. Let \mathcal{P} be a set of distributions with finite expected values. Furthermore, let $\mu^* \in \mathbb{R}$ be such that the mean of distribution $P \in \mathcal{P}$ (denoted by $\mu(P)$) satisfies the inequality $\mu(P) < \mu^*$. Then, $d_{\text{inf}}(P, \mu^*, \mathcal{P})$ is defined as follows:

$$d_{\text{inf}}(P, \mu^*, \mathcal{P}) = \inf_{\hat{P} \in \mathcal{P}} \left\{ D(P, \hat{P}) : \mu(\hat{P}) > \mu^* \right\}, \quad (1.75)$$

where $D(P, \hat{P})$ is the relative entropy between P and \hat{P} .

Provided that $\mathcal{P}_i = \{\mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma^2) : \mu_i \in \mathbb{R}, \sigma > 0\}$, we get that

$$d_{\text{inf}}(\mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma^2), \mu^*, \mathcal{P}_i) = \frac{(\mu_i - \mu^*)^2}{2\sigma^2}. \quad (1.76)$$

Theorem 1.3.3. Let $\mathcal{E} = \times_{i=1}^k \mathcal{P}_i$ be unstructured k -armed bandit environment, and $\pi \in \Pi_{\text{cons}}(\mathcal{E})$. Then for any $\nu = (P_a : a \in [k]) \in \mathcal{E}$

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{R_n(\pi, \nu)}{\log n} \geq c^*(\nu, \mathcal{E}) = \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \frac{\Delta_i}{d_{\text{inf}}(P_i, \mu^*, \mathcal{P}_i)}, \quad (1.77)$$

where $\mu^* = \max_{i \in [k]} \mu_i$ (recall that $\mu_i = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x dP_i(x)$), and $\Delta_i = \mu^* - \mu_i$ is the suboptimality gap of action $i \in [k]$.

Note that $c^*(\nu, \mathcal{E})$ lower bound is instance dependent. By equation (1.76), for $\nu \in \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{N}}^k(1)$ bandits we have the following theoretical asymptotic lower bound for $R_n(\pi, \nu)$:

$$c^*(\nu, \mathcal{E}) = \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \frac{\Delta_i}{d_{\text{inf}}(P_i, \mu^*, \mathcal{P}_i)} = \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \frac{\Delta_i}{\frac{(\mu_i - \mu^*)^2}{2}} = \sum_{i: \Delta_i > 0} \frac{2}{\Delta_i}, \quad (1.78)$$

which matches with the asymptotic upper bound from Theorem 1.3.2, what explains the name of Algorithm 2.

Chapter 2

Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS)

The problem area of estimating models from observed data can be dealt with finite-sample system identification methods [16]. We give an overview of a statistical approach called Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS) method, which can build distribution-free confidence regions for parameterized but unknown systems. Later, we use this method in multi-armed bandit problems, where each bandit arm can be interpreted as a quite simple random scalar system. At the beginning of this section we present a general finite-sample system identification framework (based on [8]) in which Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS) fits. SPS is to be thoroughly analysed in the following section.

Let us consider output measurements $(Y_i)_{i=1}^n = (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n)$, which form an observable sequence of random variables. Assume that these observations depend on two other sequences:

- past measured inputs $(U_i)_{i=1}^n = (U_1, U_2, \dots, U_n)$, and
- past inputs $(W_i)_{i=1}^n = (W_1, W_2, \dots, W_n)$ that cannot be directly measured, which can be interpreted as noise.

The outputs may also depend on a set of initial assumptions \mathcal{F} . The connection of these random sequences can be expressed in the following system:

$$(Y_i)_{i=1}^n = f((U_i)_{i=1}^n, (W_i)_{i=1}^n, \mathcal{F}). \quad (2.1)$$

Consequently, $(Y_i)_{i=1}^n$ is the function of inputs and initial conditions. Define a family of functions $\{f((U_t)_{t=1}^n, (W_t)_{t=1}^n, \mathcal{F}; \theta)\}$ parameterized by θ , and assume that exists θ^* for which $f((U_t)_{t=1}^n, (W_t)_{t=1}^n, \mathcal{F}; \theta^*) = f((U_t)_{t=1}^n, (W_t)_{t=1}^n, \mathcal{F})$, namely it gives back the original sampling mechanism. The fundamental identification goal is to give an estimate of θ^* by constructing a confidence set $\hat{\Theta}_n$, such that

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n) = p \quad (2.2)$$

for pre-determined probability $p \in (0, 1)$. This is quite a general scheme, and there

are assumptions to be made to construct such confidence set. The first is that the nonmeasured noises W_t ($t \in [n]$) can be retrieved from $(U_t)_{t=1}^n, (Y_i)_{i=1}^n, \mathcal{F}$. The second assumption states that $(W_1, W_2, \dots, W_n) \sim (\sigma_1 W_1, \sigma_2 W_2, \dots, \sigma_n W_n)$ for all sign sequences $\{\sigma_t\}_{t=1}^n \in \{-1, 1\}^n$, thus the n -dimensional sequence is jointly symmetric around the origin.

2.1 Construction of SPS confidence regions for linear systems

In what follows, we present a certain way to construct the confidence region $\hat{\Theta}_n$ that satisfies (2.2), as well we review and examine all the useful properties one would expect from such a point estimation via confidence sets. The particular approach, called Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS) method, provides finite-sample, non-asymptotic estimate of the parameter based on the observed data. The construction depends on mild statistical assumptions. In case of SPS confidence sets, the inclusion of the true parameter of the sampling mechanism holds with exact probability. The backbone of the track of thought is [9] and [10] by Csáji et al.

Let's consider a linear data generating system

$$Y_t = \varphi_t^T \theta^* + N_t, \quad (2.3)$$

where $Y_t \in \mathbb{R}$ is the measured output (a random variable), $\varphi_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the control variable (the regressor, that is considered to be deterministic) that corresponds to U_t (from the general framework), and N_t is the random noise (that corresponds to W_t), which all are indexed by discrete time $t \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Lastly, the constant $\theta^* \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the unknown parameter, which characterizes the system.

To advance further in the theory of the SPS method, one should be familiar with symmetric random variables [14].

Definition 2.1.1. Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a probability space and $X : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a real-valued random variable (i.e. $\mathcal{F}/\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ measurable, where $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$ is the Borel σ -algebra of \mathbb{R}). Then X is called symmetric about $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$ if for every $E \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R})$

$$\mathbb{P}(X - \mu \in E) \doteq \mathbb{P}(-(X - \mu) \in E), \quad (2.4)$$

where $\mathbb{P}\{X - \mu \in E\} = \mathbb{P}(\{\omega \in \Omega : X(\omega) - \mu \in E\})$.

Remark 2.1.1. X is symmetric about zero if and only if X and $-X$ have the same distribution.

Definition 2.1.2. The sign of a real-valued random variable X is defined as follows: $\text{sgn } X = 1$ if $X \in (0, \infty)$, and $\text{sgn } X = -1$ if $X \in (-\infty, 0)$.

Lemma 2.1.1. *Let $X : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a real-valued random variable on a probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ assuming that it is symmetric about zero and $\mathbb{P}(X = 0) = 0$. Then $|X|$ (the absolute value of X) and $\text{sgn } X$ are independent.*

Proof. The symmetric property of X infers that $\mathbb{P}(X \in (0, \infty)) = \mathbb{P}(X \in (-\infty, 0)) = \frac{1}{2}$ since $\mathbb{P}(X = 0) = 0$. Let $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be an arbitrary Borel set, and let us use the notation $-E = \{-e : e \in E\}$. Furthermore, define the the positive and the negative part of E as $E^+ \doteq \{e \in E : e > 0\}$ and $E^- \doteq \{e \in E : e < 0\}$ respectively. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}\left(\{|X| \in E\} \cap \{\text{sgn } X = 1\}\right) &= \mathbb{P}\left(\{|X| \in E\} \cap \{X \in (0, \infty)\}\right) \\
&= \mathbb{P}\left(\left[\{X \in E\} \cup \{-X \in E\}\right] \cap \{X \in (0, \infty)\}\right) \\
&= \mathbb{P}\left(\left[\{X \in E\} \cap \{X \in (0, \infty)\}\right] \cup \left[\{-X \in E\} \cap \{-X \in (-\infty, 0)\}\right]\right) \\
&= \mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in E^+\} \cup \{-X \in E^-\}\right) = \mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in (E^+ \cup -E^-)\}\right), \tag{2.5}
\end{aligned}$$

where we used set theory and the fact that $\{X \in (0, \infty)\} = \{-X \in (-\infty, 0)\}$. On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}\left(\{|X| \in E\}\right) \cdot \mathbb{P}\left(\{\text{sgn } X = 1\}\right) &= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{|X| \in E\}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in E \setminus \{0\}\} \cup \{-X \in E \setminus \{0\}\}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}(X = 0) \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in E^+\} \cup \{X \in E^-\} \cup \{-X \in E^+\} \cup \{-X \in E^-\}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in E^+\} \cup \{X \in -E^-\} \cup \{X \in E^-\} \cup \{X \in -E^+\}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in (E^+ \cup -E^-)\} \cup \{X \in (E^- \cup -E^+)\}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in (E^+ \cup -E^-)\}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in (E^- \cup -E^+)\}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{X \in (E^+ \cup -E^-)\}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{P}\left(\{-X \in (-E^- \cup E^+)\}\right) \\
&= \mathbb{P}\left(X \in (E^+ \cup -E^-)\right) \tag{2.6}
\end{aligned}$$

by the observation that the two sets $\{X \in (E^+ \cup -E^-)\} \subseteq (0, \infty)$ and $\{X \in (E^- \cup -E^+)\} \subseteq (-\infty, 0)$ are disjoint, as well as exploiting the symmetry of X in the last equation. Putting equation (2.5) and (2.6) together we get

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\{|X| \in E\}\right) \cdot \mathbb{P}\left(\{\text{sgn } X = 1\}\right) = \mathbb{P}\left(\{|X| \in E\} \cap \{\text{sgn } X = 1\}\right). \tag{2.7}$$

By similar argument, one can prove the independence of events $\{|X| \in E\}$ and $\{\text{sgn } X = -1\}$. $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ was an arbitrary Borel set, which concludes the proof of independence of $|X|$ and $\text{sgn } X$ in case of $\mathbb{P}(X = 0) = 0$. \square

Remark 2.1.2. If X is not symmetric about zero, then the independence of $|X|$ and

$\text{sgn } X$ does not hold in general. For instance, consider the following probability density function:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{4}{3}(1-x) & , \text{ if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ \frac{4}{3}(2x+1) & , \text{ if } -\frac{1}{2} \leq x \leq 0, \end{cases} \quad (2.8)$$

and take $E = [0, 1/2]$, then

$$\mathbb{P}(|X| \in E | \text{sgn } X = 1) = \frac{\mathbb{P}(|X| \in E, \text{sgn } X = 1)}{\mathbb{P}(\text{sgn } X = 1)} = \frac{\mathbb{P}(X \in E)}{\mathbb{P}\left(X \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right]\right)} = \frac{\frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{3}{8}}{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{3}{4}, \quad (2.9)$$

but

$$\mathbb{P}(|X| \in E) = \mathbb{P}\left(X \in \left[-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right]\right) = \frac{5}{6}. \quad (2.10)$$

Therefore, the sign and the absolute value of X are dependent. Furthermore, in this particular case, the greater the $|X|$, the more likely its sign to be positive.

Remark 2.1.3. Notice that assumption $\mathbb{P}(X = 0) = 0$ in Lemma 2.1.1 only matters in case of discrete random variables. Consider the following example of a discrete random variable X that is symmetric about 0: let $\mathbb{P}(X = -2) = \mathbb{P}(X = 2) = 1/9$, $\mathbb{P}(X = -1) = \mathbb{P}(X = 1) = 2/9$ and $\mathbb{P}(X = 0) = 1/3$. Then for $E \doteq [0, 1]$

$$\mathbb{P}(|X| \in E, \text{sgn } X = 1) = \mathbb{P}(X \in (0, 1]) = \mathbb{P}(X = 1) = \frac{2}{9}, \quad (2.11)$$

but

$$\mathbb{P}(|X| \in E) \cdot \mathbb{P}(\text{sgn } X = 1) = \mathbb{P}(X \in [-1, 1]) \frac{1}{3} = \frac{7}{24}, \quad (2.12)$$

this the sign and the absolute value of X are dependent.

We make two core assumptions regarding the SPS method:

- (I) $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$ is a sequence of independent symmetric random variables about zero, and $\mathbb{P}(N_t = 0) = 0$ for $t \in [n]$.
- (II) Define matrix R_n as the sum of the dyads $\varphi_t \varphi_t^T$ for $t \in [n]$:

$$R_n \doteq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T. \quad (2.13)$$

Then we assume that R_n is invertible, i.e. $\det R_n \neq 0$.

Remark 2.1.4. Note that there are no requirements regarding the moments or the density function of N_t . Also recall that in order to satisfy (II), $n \geq d$ must hold (necessary

but not sufficient condition), because the rank of a dyad is 1, and the rank of the sum of n dyads is at most d . On the other hand, if the span of $(\varphi_t)_{t=1}^n$ is \mathbb{R}^d , then R_n is surely invertible.

Definition 2.1.3. A Rademacher random variable α takes values from $\{-1, 1\}$ equiprobably, i.e. $\mathbb{P}(\alpha = 1) = \mathbb{P}(\alpha = -1) = \frac{1}{2}$.

Remark 2.1.5. Rademacher random variables will often be referred as random signs. Furthermore, they are symmetric about zero.

In order to construct the finite-sample and exact confidence region $\hat{\Theta}_n$ for the unknown parameter θ^* one has to define $m - 1$ sign-perturbed sums

$$\begin{aligned} H_i(\theta) &= \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) = \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t (\varphi_t^T \theta^* + N_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t \varphi_t^T (\theta^* - \theta) + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t N_t = \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \bar{\theta} + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t N_t, \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

where $\bar{\theta} = \theta^* - \theta$, and $(\alpha_{i,t})_{i=1, t=1}^{m-1, n}$ are independent and identically distributed random signs. Furthermore, a reference sum is defined as

$$H_0(\theta) = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \bar{\theta} + \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t N_t. \quad (2.15)$$

For θ^* the reference sum and the perturbed sums take special forms:

$$H_0(\theta^*) = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t N_t, \quad (2.16)$$

$$H_i(\theta^*) = \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t N_t \doteq \sum_{t=1}^n \pm \varphi_t N_t. \quad (2.17)$$

In order to provide intuitive understanding, we give a brief introduction on why we have defined these particular sums. First, the definition of the sums suggest that $H_0(\theta^*)$ and $H_i(\theta^*)$ should have the same distribution due to the fact that their defining noise sequence is independent and symmetric about the origin, thus random sign perturbation should not affect their distribution.

We intend to compare the reference sums $H_i(\theta)$ with $H_0(\theta)$, thus some kind of norm should be used for this matter since they are d -dimensional vectors. Choosing the Euclidean norm $\|\cdot\|_2$ on \mathbb{R}^d , and comparing $\|H_0(\theta^*)\|_2$ with $\|H_i(\theta^*)\|_2$ one presumes that neither of $\|H_i(\theta^*)\|_2$ for $i \in [m - 1]$ should be greater or less than $\|H_0(\theta^*)\|_2$ due to the previous argument. More precisely, considering the sorting of $\{\|H_i(\theta^*)\|_2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ in ascending order, each $\|H_i(\theta^*)\|_2$ (for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$) should take each position equiprobably (with probability $1/m$) in the order. On the other hand, if $\theta \neq \theta^*$, and

$\|\bar{\theta}\|_2$ is "sufficiently large", then $\sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \bar{\theta}$ grows faster in norm than $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \bar{\theta}$, hence

$$\left\| \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \bar{\theta} + \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t N_t \right\|_2 > \left\| \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \bar{\theta} + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t N_t \right\|_2 \quad (2.18)$$

could be the case "most likely". If this is the case indeed, then $\|H_0(\theta)\|_2$ has higher rank in the ordering of $\{\|H_i(\theta)\|_2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$, thus choosing a confidence set that contains only $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$ elements for which $H_0(\theta)$ takes a "low rank" in the ascending order, then we presumably receive a set that contains vectors which are close to θ^* in norm. In what follows, we present the translation of these intuitions into proper formulations.

First and foremost, we finally define the confidence set using the $m-1$ sign-perturbed sums and the reference sum. In order to shape the region, instead of $H_0(\theta)$ and $H_i(\theta)$, we introduce the sums $S_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} H_i(\theta)$ for $i \in [m-1]$, which are well defined since $R_n = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T$ is sum of dyads, hence it is positive semidefinite. Furthermore, by assumption (II) $\det R_n \neq 0$, thus R_n is not only positive semidefinite but positive definite, which concludes that its root and inverse of $R_n^{1/2}$ exist. This transformation does not affect the construction itself and it helps to shape the confidence regions.

Algorithm 3 (SPS-initialization)

1. Set probability level $p = 1 - q/m$, where $q, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+ : m > q > 0$.
 2. Let $R_n = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T$, factor R_n such that $R_n = R_n^{1/2} R_n^{1/2}$.
 3. Generate $n(m-1)$ random signs $(\alpha_{i,t})_{i=1, t=1}^{m-1, n}$ independently from Rademacher distribution.
 4. Generate a π permutation on $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$ uniformly.
 5. Define \prec_π strict total order on any m real numbers z_0, \dots, z_{m-1} such that $z_i \prec_\pi z_j$ if and only if $(z_i < z_j)$ or $(z_i = z_j, \text{ but } \pi(i) < \pi(j))$.
-

The SPS method consists of two parts: the initialization (Algorithm 3), and the indicator (Algorithm 4). The former presets the global parameters of the procedure. In addition, the latter, which is called SPS-indicator, is the algorithm that determines whether or not a particular $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is in the confidence set $\hat{\Theta}_n$. Regarding the SPS-initialization, note that generating a permutation uniformly means that out of all the possible number of permutations (all in all $m!$) a certain one is chosen with probability $1/m!$. The relation defined in the final part of SPS-initialization is truly a strict total order by definition 2.1.4. Considering SPS-indicator, we say that $\mathcal{R}_0(\theta) = k$ if the reference value is the k^{th} smallest according to \prec_π in the ordering.

Algorithm 4 (SPS-indicator(θ))

1. For input vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m-1\}$ let

$$S_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta),$$

$$S_0(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta).$$

2. Sort $\{\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ according to \prec_π . Let $\mathcal{R}_0(\theta)$ denote the rank of the reference value $\|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$ in the ordering.
 3. If $\mathcal{R}_0(\theta) \leq m - q$ return 1, else return 0.
-

Now we define the SPS confidence region in case of an n -element sample as follows:

$$\hat{\Theta}_n = \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \text{SPS-indicator}(\theta) = 1\}. \quad (2.19)$$

Theorem 2.1.2. *If Assumption (I) and (II) hold, then*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n) = 1 - \frac{q}{m}. \quad (2.20)$$

Before showing that $\hat{\Theta}_n$ contains the unknown parameter of the system with user-chosen probability $p = 1 - q/m$, it is required to get through some technical details first. See [10] as reference for the next three lemmas.

Lemma 2.1.3. *Let $\beta, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k$ be independent Rademacher random variables. Then $\beta, \beta\alpha_1, \beta\alpha_2, \dots, \beta\alpha_k$ are also independent Rademacher random variables.*

Proof. For any $i \in [k]$, $\beta\alpha_i \in \{-1, 1\}$ almost surely, and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\beta\alpha_i = 1) &= \mathbb{P}(\{\beta = 1, \alpha = 1\} \cup \{\beta = -1, \alpha = -1\}) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(\{\beta = 1, \alpha = 1\}) + \mathbb{P}(\{\beta = -1, \alpha = -1\}) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(\{\beta = 1\})\mathbb{P}(\{\alpha = 1\}) + \mathbb{P}(\{\beta = -1\})\mathbb{P}(\{\alpha = -1\}) = \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

Similarly, $\mathbb{P}(\beta\alpha_i = -1) = \frac{1}{2}$, thus $\beta\alpha_i$ is indeed Rademacher variable for every $i \in [k]$. Define the numbers s_0, s_1, \dots, s_k to be fixed signs, i.e. $s_i \in \{-1, 1\}$ for $i \in \{0, \dots, k\}$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbb{P}(\beta = s_0, \beta\alpha_1 = s_1, \dots, \beta\alpha_k = s_k) \\
&= \mathbb{P}(\beta = s_0, s_0\alpha_1 = s_1, \dots, s_0\alpha_k = s_k) \\
&= \mathbb{P}(\beta = s_0, s_0^2\alpha_1 = s_0s_1, \dots, s_0^2\alpha_k = s_0s_k) \\
&= \mathbb{P}(\beta = s_0, \alpha_1 = s_0s_1, \dots, \alpha_k = s_0s_k) \\
&= \mathbb{P}(\beta = s_0) \cdot \mathbb{P}(\alpha_1 = s_0s_1) \cdot \dots \cdot \mathbb{P}(\alpha_k = s_0s_k) \\
&= \mathbb{P}(\beta = s_0) \cdot \mathbb{P}(\beta\alpha_1 = s_1) \cdot \dots \cdot \mathbb{P}(\beta\alpha_k = s_k), \tag{2.22}
\end{aligned}$$

where the third equality holds, since $s_0^2 = 1$ regardless of the value of s_0 . In addition, the penultimate equation comes from the independence assumption. At the final equation, we have used the fact that $\mathbb{P}(\alpha_i = s_0s_i) = \mathbb{P}(\beta\alpha_i = s_i) = \frac{1}{2}$, since $\beta\alpha_i$ is also a Rademacher random variable. \square

Lemma 2.1.4. *Let X and Y be independent random variables that take values in \mathbb{R}^d and \mathbb{R}^k respectively. Furthermore, let $g : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable function, and $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable set. If for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ $\mathbb{P}(g(x, Y) \in A) = p$, then $\mathbb{P}(g(X, Y) \in A) = p$.*

Proof. Consider $\mathbb{I}_A : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ indicator function, that is

$$\mathbb{I}_A(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \text{if } g(x, y) \in A, \\ 0 & , \text{if } g(x, y) \notin A. \end{cases} \tag{2.23}$$

Define $i_A : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as $i_A(x) = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}_A(x, Y)]$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}(g(X, Y) \in A) &= \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}\{g(X, Y) \in A\}] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}_A(X, Y)] \\
&= \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{I}_A(X, Y)|X]] = \mathbb{E}[i_A(X)] = \mathbb{E}[p] = p, \tag{2.24}
\end{aligned}$$

where we used the law of total expectations (for properties of conditional expectation see section 34 of [2]). \square

Recall the definition of strict total order from Chapter 1 of [17].

Definition 2.1.4. Let A be an arbitrary set. A binary relation \prec on A is a strict total order if

1. $\forall a \in A$ not $a \prec a$ (nonreflexivity),
2. $\forall a, b, c \in A$ if $a \prec b, b \prec c$, then $a \prec c$ (transitivity),
3. $\forall a, b \in A$ if $a \neq b$, then $(a \prec b \text{ or } b \prec a)$ (comparability).

Remark 2.1.6. Note that comparability itself does not exclude the option of both $a \prec b$ and $b \prec a$ be true at the same time, but transitivity and the irreflexive property together do.

Definition 2.1.5. Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a probability space and Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_m be a sequence of real-valued random variables on it. Consider a strict total order \prec (i.e. irreflexive, transitive and connected). If for every I permutation of $\{1, 2, \dots, m\}$

$$\mathbb{P}(Z_{I(1)} \prec Z_{I(2)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}) = \frac{1}{m!} \quad (2.25)$$

holds, then we say that Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_m sequence is uniformly ordered with respect to \prec .

Remark 2.1.7. Take two arbitrary but different permutations I, J from the symmetric group S_m (i.e. permutation group of set of m elements). Then let $l \in [m]$ be the smallest index such that $I(l) \neq J(l)$. This particular index exists since $I \neq J$. One can assume that $I(l) < J(l)$ holds because if not then just swap the role of I and J . Having premised this, notice that $\exists! k \in \{l+1, \dots, m\} : I(l) = J(k)$, and $\exists! h \in \{l+1, \dots, m\} : I(h) = J(l)$. The unique existence of l, k, h depends on the facts that I, J are bijections and $I(n) = J(n)$ if $n < l$. Now consider a sequence Z_1, \dots, Z_m that is uniformly ordered with respect to a strict total order \prec . One can observe that for the aforementioned permutations I, J , and indices k, l, h we have the following setup:

$$\begin{aligned} \{Z_{I(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(l)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(h)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}\} &\subseteq \{Z_{I(l)} \prec Z_{I(h)}\}, \\ \{Z_{J(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{J(l)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{J(k)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{J(m)}\} &\subseteq \{Z_{J(l)} \prec Z_{J(k)}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

However, due to the irreflexive property of \prec

$$\{Z_{I(l)} \prec Z_{I(h)}\} \cap \{Z_{J(l)} \prec Z_{J(k)}\} = \{Z_{J(l)} \prec Z_{J(k)} = Z_{I(l)} \prec Z_{I(h)} = Z_{J(l)}\} = \emptyset, \quad (2.27)$$

which implies that

$$\{Z_{I(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}\} \cap \{Z_{J(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{J(m)}\} = \emptyset. \quad (2.28)$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{Z} \doteq \{\{Z_{I(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}\} : I \in S_m\}$ is a family of disjoint, mutually exclusive events, hence

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{Z}) &= \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{I \in S_m} \{Z_{I(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}\}\right) = \sum_{I \in S_m} \mathbb{P}(Z_{I(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}) \\ &= m! \cdot \frac{1}{m!} = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

Moreover

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbb{P}(\{Z_i \text{ takes position } j \text{ in the ordering of } (Z_i)_{i=1}^m\}) = \\
& = \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{I \in S_m, I(j)=i} \{Z_{I(1)} \prec \cdots \prec Z_{I(m)}\}\right) = \\
& = \sum_{\substack{I \in S_m \\ I(j)=i}} \mathbb{P}(Z_{I(1)} \prec \cdots \prec Z_{I(m)}) = (m-1)! \cdot \frac{1}{m!} = \frac{1}{m}. \tag{2.30}
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently Z_i takes every position in the ordering equiprobably.

Lemma 2.1.5. *Let Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_m be independent and identically distributed, \mathbb{R} -valued random variables on $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$. Define \prec_π strict total order on m element sets as in Algorithm 3. Then $(Z_i)_{i=1}^m$ sequence is uniformly ordered with respect to \prec_π .*

Proof. For any realization $\pi(\omega)$ and $(Z_i(\omega))_{i=1}^m$ there exists a unique ordering of the sample realization with respect to \prec_π due to the fact that for $i \neq j$ $Z_i(\omega), Z_j(\omega) \in \mathbb{R}$ ($Z_i(\omega) \prec_\pi Z_j(\omega)$ or $Z_j(\omega) \prec_\pi Z_i(\omega)$) exclusively, namely both $Z_i(\omega) \prec_\pi Z_j(\omega)$ and $Z_j(\omega) \prec_\pi Z_i(\omega)$ cannot be true at the same time, but one of them will surely hold (see Remark 2.1.6). Hence, the system defined as $\mathcal{Z} \doteq \{\{Z_{I(1)} \prec \dots \prec Z_{I(m)}\} : I \in S_m\}$ gives back the complete sample space. In addition, \mathcal{Z} contains mutually exclusive events (see Remark 2.1.7), thus \mathcal{Z} forms a complete system of events.

The cardinality of \mathcal{Z} is $m!$, therefore, in order to complete the proof, one has to show that each ordering occurs with the same probability, which then cannot be other than $1/m!$. Consider two fixed permutations I, J on $[m]$ and the corresponding orderings $A_1 \doteq \{Z_{I(1)} \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z_{I(m)}\}$, $A_2 \doteq \{Z_{J(1)} \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z_{J(m)}\}$ as events. Assume that $\mathbb{P}(A_1) = p_1, \mathbb{P}(A_2) = p_2$. Define $Z'_{I(l)} \doteq Z_{J(l)}$ for $l \in [m]$ and $A_3 \doteq \{Z'_{I(1)} \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z'_{I(m)}\}$. Then $\mathbb{P}(A_1) = \mathbb{P}(A_3)$ since Z'_1, \dots, Z'_m has the same probability distribution as Z_1, \dots, Z_m by the i.i.d assumption of $(Z_i)_{i=1}^m$. Moreover, $\mathbb{P}(A_3) = \mathbb{P}(A_2)$ because $Z'_{I(l)}$ and $Z_{J(l)}$ are equal by definition, as well as by the complete symmetry of π (permutation π chosen uniformly, thus in case of tie-breaking between two realizations during the sorting according to \prec_π , either of the two orders occurs equiprobably). Summing up $\mathbb{P}(A_1) = \mathbb{P}(A_3) = \mathbb{P}(A_2)$, so any two orderings occur with the same probability, which infers that $(Z_i)_{i=1}^m$ is uniformly ordered with respect to \prec_π . \square

Now we proceed to prove the main theorem of this section (for reference see [10]).

Proof of Theorem 2.1.2. Consider the sorting of $\{\|S_i(\theta^*)\|_2^2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ in ascending order with respect to \prec_π . If $\|S_0(\theta^*)\|_2^2$ takes one of the first $m-q$ positions ($R(\theta^*) \leq m-q$), then by definition $\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n$. In case of the reference sum $S_0(\theta)$, define $\alpha_{0,t} \doteq 1$ for each $t \in [n]$. Then

$$S_i(\theta^*) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t N_t, \tag{2.31}$$

hence each $S_i(\theta^*)$ sum (for $i \in \{0, \dots, m-1\}$) can be interpreted as the function of the corresponding perturbed noise sequence $(\alpha_{i,t}N_t)_{t=1}^n$:

$$S(\alpha_{i,1}N_1, \alpha_{i,2}N_2, \dots, \alpha_{i,n}N_n) \doteq S_i(\theta^*). \quad (2.32)$$

Since N_t is symmetric about the origin and $\mathbb{P}(N_t = 0) = 0$, we can apply Lemma 2.1.1. Consequently, for all $t \in [n]$ the random variables $|N_t|$ and $\text{sgn}(N_t)$ are independent. Define $\gamma_{i,t} \doteq \alpha_{i,t} \text{sgn}(N_t)$ for $i \in [m-1] \cup \{0\}$ and $t \in [n]$. By Lemma 2.1.3 we can conclude that $\gamma_{0,t}, \gamma_{1,t}, \dots, \gamma_{m-1,t}$ are independent and identically distributed Rademacher variables due to the fact that $\text{sgn}(N_t), \alpha_{1,t}, \alpha_{2,t}, \dots, \alpha_{m-1,t}$ is an independent and identically distributed sequence of random signs. Therefore, if $i \neq j$, then $(\gamma_{i,1}, \dots, \gamma_{i,n})$ and $(\gamma_{j,1}, \dots, \gamma_{j,n})$ have the same distribution, and they are independent.

Now fix the absolute value of the noise sequence, i.e. let $|N_t| = v_t$ for all $t \in [n]$. Consider

$$Z_i(v_1, \dots, v_n, \gamma_{i,1}, \dots, \gamma_{i,n}) \doteq \|S(\gamma_{i,1}v_1, \dots, \gamma_{i,n}v_n)\|_2^2 \quad (2.33)$$

for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$. Applying the same measurable function $\|S(\cdot)\|_2^2$ to each element of the independent and identically distributed sequence $((\gamma_{i,1}, \dots, \gamma_{i,n}))_{i=0}^{m-1}$ preserves the independence and yields an identically distributed sequence. Thus, for fixed realization of $(|N_t|)_{t=1}^n$, the sample $(Z_i(v_1, \dots, v_n, \gamma_{i,1}, \dots, \gamma_{i,n}))_{i=0}^{m-1}$ is i.i.d. indeed. Moreover, by Lemma 2.1.5, it is uniformly ordered with respect to \prec_π . In turn, being uniformly ordered means that every order of $(Z_i(v_1, \dots, v_n, \gamma_{i,1}, \dots, \gamma_{i,n}))_{i=0}^{m-1}$ according to \prec_π occurs with probability $1/m!$, which does not depend on the knowledge of $\{v_t\}_{t=1}^n$ realization:

$$\mathbb{P}(Z_{I(0)}(v_1, \dots, v_n, \gamma_{0,1}, \dots, \gamma_{0,n}) \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z_{I(m-1)}(v_1, \dots, v_n, \gamma_{m-1,1}, \dots, \gamma_{m-1,n})) = \frac{1}{m!} \quad (2.34)$$

for every $(v_1, \dots, v_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and any I permutation on $\{0, \dots, m-1\}$. Hence, by Lemma 2.1.4, we receive the unconditional exact probability

$$\mathbb{P}(Z_{I(0)} \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z_{I(m-1)}) = \frac{1}{m!}, \quad (2.35)$$

where $Z_{I(i)} \doteq Z_{I(i)}(|N_1|, \dots, |N_n|, \gamma_{I(i),1}, \dots, \gamma_{I(i),n}) = \|S_{I(i)}(\theta^*)\|_2^2$. Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \Theta_n^*) &= \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{I \in \mathcal{S}_m: I(0) \in [m-q]} \{Z_{I(0)} \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z_{I(m-1)}\}\right) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{I \in \mathcal{S}_m \\ I(0) \in [m-q]}} \mathbb{P}(Z_{I(0)} \prec_\pi \dots \prec_\pi Z_{I(m-1)}) = \sum_{\substack{I \in \mathcal{S}_m \\ I(0) \in [m-q]}} \frac{1}{m!} \\ &= \frac{(m-q) \cdot (m-1)!}{m!} = 1 - \frac{q}{m}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.36}$$

using disjunction of events (see Remark 2.1.7). \square

Remark 2.1.8. What would happen if we fixed the realization of $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$ instead of $(|N_t|)_{t=1}^n$ in the proof of Theorem 2.1.2? If this had been the case, $S_0(\theta^*)$ would not have been a random variable at all, hence we would not have gained an i.i.d. sequence, which was required to receive a uniformly ordered sequence.

2.2 Properties of the SPS method

In this part of the thesis, we give an overview of many useful properties of the SPS finite-sample confidence region construction method based on [10] and [11]. In addition, we examine the probability of the events that the confidence set becomes empty or unbounded. We also show how sign-perturbation can be generalized to symmetric-perturbation, and we consider other possible modifications of the SPS method.

2.2.1 Unbounded sets, empty regions, and the inclusion of the Least-Squares estimate in the confidence set

First of all, we examine the inclusion of the least-squares estimate (LSE) $\hat{\theta}_n$ in the confidence set $\hat{\Theta}_n$ (see [10]). By definition the LSE can be obtained as the minimum of the squared error function:

$$\hat{\theta}_n = \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta)^2. \tag{2.37}$$

Hence, by using the notation $\mathbf{0}$ for the d -dimensional zero vector we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta)^2 &= -2 \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) = \mathbf{0} \\ \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t Y_t &= \theta \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \\ \hat{\theta}_n &\doteq \left(\sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \right)^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t Y_t, \end{aligned} \quad (2.38)$$

which is well defined (the inverse of $\sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T$ exists) if assumption (II) holds. This is the minimum of the squared error indeed, since

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta)^2 = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} 2 \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) = 2 \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^T, \quad (2.39)$$

which is positive semidefinite in general, but under (II) it becomes positive definite. Moreover, notice that

$$H_0(\hat{\theta}_n) = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \hat{\theta}_n) = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.40)$$

because $H_0(\theta)$ is constant times the first derivative of the squared error function. On the other hand, in general, the squared norm of a sign-perturbed sum does not have root in $\hat{\theta}_n$. If that is the case indeed, then it means that the LSE is in the confidence set. However, regardless of the underlying sampling mechanism (which yields $(Y_t)_{t=1}^n$), it has non-zero probability that $\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset$, consequently, the LSE is not in the confidence set. This phenomenon is related to the case when $\hat{\theta}_n$ becomes the root of $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2$ for some $i \in [m-1]$. As our contribution to the theory of SPS method, we examine the probability of this event.

If for an $i \in [m-1]$ $\alpha_{i,1} = \dots = \alpha_{i,n} \in \{1, -1\}$ (therefore, $H_i(\theta) = H_0(\theta)$ or $H_i(\theta) = -H_0(\theta)$), then $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$. Hence, when there are at least $m-q$ reference sums (indexed by \mathcal{I}) whose all perturbation signs $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ are solely plus ones or minus ones, and exists $\tilde{\mathcal{I}} \subseteq \mathcal{I} : |\tilde{\mathcal{I}}| = m-q$ such that for $j \in \tilde{\mathcal{I}}$ we have $\pi(j) < \pi(0)$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset$. We are interested in determining the probability of this event.

Remark 2.2.1. From now on, we will use the notation $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ when $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ is either constant 1 or constant -1 sequence.

Remark 2.2.2. Consider the following case as an example. If $\{\varphi_1, \varphi_2\}$ is chosen to be

the standard basis of \mathbb{R}^2 , then assumption (II) is satisfied, and

$$H_i(\theta) = \sum_{t=1}^2 \varphi_t \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) = (\alpha_{i,1}(Y_1 - \theta_1), \alpha_{i,2}(Y_2 - \theta_2))^T, \quad (2.41)$$

but $H_0(\theta) = (Y_1 - \theta_1, Y_2 - \theta_2)^T$, thus $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$ for every $i \in [m-1]$ regardless of $\alpha_{i,1}, \alpha_{i,2}$ and Y_1, Y_2 .

Next, we analyse the event $\bigcup_{\sigma \in \{-1,1\}} \bigcap_{t=1}^n \{\alpha_{i,t} = \sigma\} = \{(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}\}$, which implies the occurrence of $\{\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2\}$. Later, we will examine a special case of one-dimensional SPS. In that particular case, the equiprobability of these two events always true regardless of the noise and the regressors.

Consider that the squared norm of certain perturbed sum equals to the reference value $\|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$ with probability at least $2 \cdot (1/2)^n = 1/(2^{n-1})$. Define $E_{\mathcal{I}}$ and $\bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\mathcal{I}} &= \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}\}, \\ \bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}} &= \bigcap_{\substack{i \in [m-1] \\ i \notin \mathcal{I}}} \{(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n \neq \pm \mathbf{1}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.42)$$

For $\mathcal{J} \neq \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{J} \subseteq [m-1], |\mathcal{J}| = k$ we have $(\bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I}}) \cap (\bar{E}_{\mathcal{J}} \cap E_{\mathcal{J}}) = \emptyset$, since for every $i \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{J}$ index $\{(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}\} \in E_{\mathcal{I}}$, but $\{(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n \neq \pm \mathbf{1}\} \in \bar{E}_{\mathcal{J}}$. Hence, $\bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I}}$ and $\bar{E}_{\mathcal{J}} \cap E_{\mathcal{J}}$ are disjoint. In addition, $\bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}}$ and $E_{\mathcal{I}}$ are independent since $(\alpha_{i,t})_{i=1, t=1}^{m-1, n}$ are i.i.d. signs. Thus, the probability of the event that $\{(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}\}$ occurs for exactly k different $i \in [m-1]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} p(m, k, n) &\doteq \mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=k}} (E_{\mathcal{I}} \cap \bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}}) \right) = \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=k}} \mathbb{P}(E_{\mathcal{I}} \cap \bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}}) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=k}} \mathbb{P}(E_{\mathcal{I}}) \mathbb{P}(\bar{E}_{\mathcal{I}}) = \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=k}} \left(\frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \right)^k \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \right)^{m-1-k} \\ &= \binom{m-1}{k} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \right)^k \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \right)^{m-1-k}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.43)$$

In order to advance further, next, we answer a general question regarding the discussed problem. Assume that π is a uniformly random permutation on $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$, i.e. $\mathbb{P}(\pi(0) = i_0, \dots, \pi(m-1) = i_{m-1}) = 1/m!$ for every (i_0, \dots, i_{m-1}) permutations of $0, \dots, m-1$. What is the probability that $\pi(0) = r$, $\pi(i) < \pi(0)$ (for $i \in \mathcal{L}$), and $\pi(j) > \pi(0)$ (for $j \in \mathcal{H}$) hold, for any partition of the set $\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{H} \subseteq [m-1]$, where $|\mathcal{L}| = l, |\mathcal{H}| = h$? Note that \mathcal{I} is a fixed set here, which has a cardinality of $l + h$. We also assume that $l \leq r$ and $h \leq m-1-r$ to avoid the case that described event is

empty. Define the following events:

$$E_{\mathcal{L}} \doteq \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{L}} \{\pi(i) < \pi(0)\} \quad (2.44)$$

$$E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}} \doteq \bigcap_{j \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}} \{\pi(j) > \pi(0)\} \quad (2.45)$$

Notice that if $\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{I}$, $|\mathcal{L}_1| = |\mathcal{L}_2| = l$ and $\mathcal{L}_1 \neq \mathcal{L}_2$, then $\forall i \in \mathcal{L}_1 \setminus \mathcal{L}_2$ $\{\pi(i) < \pi(0)\} \in E_{\mathcal{L}_1}$ but $\{\pi(i) > \pi(0)\} \in E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}_2}$, which implies that $E_{\mathcal{L}_1} \cap E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}_1}$ and $E_{\mathcal{L}_2} \cap E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}_2}$ are exclusive events. Using this formalization, the sought probability is

$$\begin{aligned} P_r(m, l, h) &= \mathbb{P} \left(\{\pi(0) = r\} \cap \bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{L}: \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{I} \\ |\mathcal{L}| = l}} (E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}}) \right) = \\ &= \mathbb{P} \left(\bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{L}: \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{I} \\ |\mathcal{L}| = l}} (E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}} \cap \{\pi(0) = r\}) \right) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{L}: \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{I} \\ |\mathcal{L}| = l}} \mathbb{P} (E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}} \cap \{\pi(0) = r\}) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{L}: \mathcal{L} \subseteq \mathcal{I} \\ |\mathcal{L}| = l}} \frac{r!}{(r-l)!} \cdot \frac{(m-r-1)!}{(m-r-h-1)!} \cdot (m-(l+h+1))! \cdot \frac{1}{m!} \\ &= \binom{h+l}{l} \frac{r!}{(r-l)!} \cdot \frac{(m-r-1)!}{(m-r-h-1)!} \cdot \frac{(m-(l+h+1))!}{m!}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

The result above was obtained by counting all the possible realizations of π , namely every order of $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$, which satisfies $E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}} \cap \{\pi(0) = r\}$, and using that each order occurs with probability $1/m!$. In details, $E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap \{\pi(0) = r\}$ means that l chosen index (precisely the elements of \mathcal{L}) can take any value from $\{0, \dots, r-1\}$, which can manifest in $\frac{r!}{(r-l)!}$ different ways. 0 takes the fixed r position. $E_{\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}} \cap \{\pi(0) = r\}$ occurs when h fixed elements (precisely the elements of $\mathcal{I} \setminus \mathcal{L}$) take position solely from $\{r+1, \dots, m-1\}$, which gives $\frac{(m-r-1)!}{(m-r-1-h)!}$ possibilities. Finally, the number of possible orders of the remaining $m-l-h-1$ elements is exactly $(m-(l+h+1))!$. This argument is independent of \mathcal{L} itself (only its cardinality matters, which is always l), and holds for any l element subset of $l+h$ element set \mathcal{I} , hence, we get the $\binom{h+l}{l}$ factor.

If there are $l+h$ perturbed sums for which $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$, then what is the probability of the event that exactly l of them are ordered lower and h higher than the reference

value with respect to \prec_π ? This happens exactly when $\bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{L}:\mathcal{L}\subseteq\mathcal{I} \\ |\mathcal{L}|=l}}(E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I}\setminus\mathcal{L}})$ occurs:

$$P(m, l, h) \doteq \mathbb{P}\left(\bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{L}:\mathcal{L}\subseteq\mathcal{I} \\ |\mathcal{L}|=l}}(E_{\mathcal{L}} \cap E_{\mathcal{I}\setminus\mathcal{L}})\right) = \sum_{r=l}^{m-h-1} P_r(m, l, h). \quad (2.47)$$

We have collected every piece of information to answer the question regarding the emptiness of the SPS confidence regions. When there are at least $m - q$ number of $i \in [m - 1]$ (indexed by \mathcal{I} , $|\mathcal{I}| = k \geq m - q$) for which $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$, and at least $m - q$ of them are ranked lower than the reference value, i.e. $\pi(0) > \pi(i)$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset$. This is the case when $l \in \{m - q, \dots, m - 1\}$ number of them are ranked lower and correspondingly $h = k - l$ are ranked higher. Thus the sought probability can be bounded as

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset) \geq \sum_{k=m-q}^{m-1} p(m, k, n) \sum_{l=m-q}^k P(m, l, k - l). \quad (2.48)$$

On top of that, using $p(m, k, n)$ and $P(l, k, m)$, we can estimate the probability of unbounded confidence regions, i.e. we bound the probability of the event that $\forall \theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \theta \in \hat{\Theta}_n$. This occurs when there are at least q number of sign-perturbed sums, indexed by \mathcal{J} , that satisfy $(\alpha_{j,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$, and at least q indices from \mathcal{J} satisfy the inequality $\pi(0) < \pi(j)$. Notice that this problem is closely related to the empty set case, and by similar argument it can be derived that

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}^d) \geq \sum_{k=q}^{m-1} p(m, k, n) \sum_{h=q}^k P(m, k - h, h). \quad (2.49)$$

Figure 2.1: Lower estimates in case of $m = 100$, $q = 5$

In addition, we note that it may be possible that the an SPS region is not bounded and does not equal to \mathbb{R}^d . In the next section, we will present an example when this

Figure 2.2: Lower estimates in case of $m = 100, q = 1$

can happen. On the other hand, in the final chapter of the thesis we will see that in case of one-dimensional SPS, the confidence region is either \mathbb{R} or bounded.

In order to interpret the results, we show the exact values of the lower bounds for certain choices of m and q . They are reported in Figure 2.1, Figure 2.2 and Table 2.1, where the figures were made with the Python programming language.

Sample size	1	2	3	4
Probability	0.2	0.0125	0.00078125	4.8828125e-05

Table 2.1: Probability of empty sets ($m = 5, q = 1$)

The lower bounds (2.48) and (2.49) are independent of the dimension, and later we will show that in case of one-dimensional SPS, estimation (2.49) is upper bound regardless of the noise, and right hand side of (2.48) is upper bound too if the noise is continuous. Although the presented shortcomings have nonzero probability, the more important case, i.e. the case of empty region, occurs with negligible probability. If m and q are fixed, then both of the obtained lower bounds decay exponentially fast as the number of observed samples n increases. The probability of empty set is always q/m if $n = 1$, and for larger sample sizes it is quite close to zero: for $m = 100, q = 5$ and $n = 2$ we get 0 rounded to 20 decimals, which is the reason why we have chosen to present a rather small example in Table 2.1. As one could expect, for fixed $m - 1$ number of perturbed sums, if q is decreased ($1 \leq q \leq m - 1$), then the confidence level is increased, and $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is more likely to be unbounded. On the other hand, if q is increased, then the probability of the occurrence of empty confidence region increases. According to the

examples reported in Figure 2.1, 2.2, the probability of the occurrence of unbounded regions is significant if one desires to construct high confidence level region in case of small sample size.

Remark 2.2.3. For $n = 1$ $\mathbb{P}(\{\hat{\Theta}_1 = \emptyset\} \cup \{\hat{\Theta}_1 = \mathbb{R}^d\}) = 1$ because

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{P}(\{\hat{\Theta}_1 = \emptyset\} \cup \{\hat{\Theta}_1 = \mathbb{R}^d\}) &= \mathbb{P}(\{\hat{\Theta}_1 = \emptyset\}) + \mathbb{P}(\{\hat{\Theta}_1 = \mathbb{R}^d\}) \\
&\geq \sum_{l=m-q}^{m-1} P(m, l, m-1-l) + \sum_{h=q}^{m-1} P(m, m-1-h, h) \\
&= \sum_{l=m-q}^{m-1} P(m, l, m-1-l) + \sum_{h=0}^{m-q-1} P(m, m-1-h-q, q+h) \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} P(m, j, m-1-j) = 1
\end{aligned} \tag{2.50}$$

using that if $k = m - 1$, then $p(m, k, 1) = 1$, and otherwise $p(m, k, n) = 0$. Therefore, in case of one-element sample, the SPS region is either the whole space or an empty set.

2.2.2 Shape of the SPS confidence regions

In what follows, we examine the shape of SPS confidence regions in general. At the end of the discussion we present the main theoretical result regarding the shape based on [10]. As the first step we show that $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2$ can be represented as a quadratic form for each $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 &= \left\| \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t(Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \right\|_2^2 \\
&= \left[\frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t(Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \right]^T \left[\frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t(Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{n^2} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t(Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \right]^T R_n^{-1} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t(Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{n^2} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t \varphi_t^T \theta - \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t Y_t \right]^T R_n^{-1} \left[\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \varphi_t(Y_t - \varphi_t^T \theta) \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{n^2} \left[\Phi^T D_i \Phi \theta - \Phi^T D_i \Upsilon \right]^T R_n^{-1} \left[\Phi^T D_i \Phi \theta - \Phi^T D_i \Upsilon \right] \\
&= \left[Q_i \theta - \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T D_i \Upsilon \right]^T R_n^{-1} \left[Q_i \theta - \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T D_i \Upsilon \right] \\
&= \theta^T Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i \theta - 2\theta^T Q_i R_n^{-1} \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T D_i \Upsilon + \frac{1}{n} (\Phi^T D_i \Upsilon)^T R_n^{-1} \frac{1}{n} (\Phi^T D_i \Upsilon), \tag{2.51}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi = (\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n)^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$, $D_i = \text{Diag}(\alpha_{i,1}, \dots, \alpha_{i,n})$ ($\text{Diag}(\cdot)$ yields diagonal matrix, which diagonal elements are the input elements in the given order), $Q_i = \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top D_i \Phi$ and $\Upsilon = (Y_1, \dots, Y_n)^\top$. $R_n = \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top \Phi$ is symmetric, as well as invertible (by assumption (II)). We also used that $R_n^{-1/2}$ is symmetric ($R_n^{-1/2} R_n^{-1/2} = R_n^{-1} = (R_n^{-1})^\top = (R_n^{-1/2} R_n^{-1/2})^\top = (R_n^{-1/2})^\top (R_n^{-1/2})^\top$), so $R_n^{-1/2} = (R_n^{-1/2})^\top$. Later, we will use the notation $\eta_i = \frac{1}{n} (\Phi^\top D_i \Upsilon)$.

For the next step we expand the squared norm of the reference sum. Recall that $\hat{\theta}_n = (\Phi^\top \Phi)^{-1} \Phi^\top \Upsilon$, $R_n \hat{\theta}_n = \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top \Upsilon$, and define $Q_0 \doteq \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top \Phi = R_n$. Then, using (2.51) formula, we can obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 &= \theta^\top R_n \theta - 2\theta^\top \frac{1}{n} \Phi^\top \Upsilon + \frac{1}{n} (\Phi^\top \Upsilon)^\top R_n^{-1} \frac{1}{n} (\Phi^\top \Upsilon) \\ &= \theta^\top R_n \theta - 2\theta^\top R_n \hat{\theta}_n + (R_n \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n^{-1} R_n \hat{\theta}_n \\ &= (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n). \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

Consider that $\hat{\Theta}_n$ can be written as the union of intersection of sets:

$$\hat{\Theta}_n = \bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=q}} \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 \prec_\pi \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}. \quad (2.53)$$

Where the set $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 \prec_\pi \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}$ is either $\mathcal{E}_i \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 \leq \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}$ or $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_i \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 < \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}$ based on the particular π . Therefore, we intend to analyze $F_i(\theta) = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 - \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2$ real function to understand the shape of $\hat{\Theta}_n$.

$$\begin{aligned} F_i(\theta) &= (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^\top R_n (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n) - \theta^\top Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i \theta + 2\theta^\top Q_i R_n^{-1} \eta_i - \eta_i^\top R_n^{-1} \eta_i \\ &= \theta^\top (R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i) \theta - 2\theta^\top (R_n \hat{\theta}_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} \eta_i) + \hat{\theta}_n^\top R_n \hat{\theta}_n - \eta_i^\top R_n^{-1} \eta_i \end{aligned} \quad (2.54)$$

To advance in the analysis of the obtained quadratic form in (2.54) the following lemma is required.

Lemma 2.2.1. *For $i \in [m-1]$ under assumption (II) the matrix $R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i$ is positive semidefinite.*

Before proving this lemma, one should be familiar with the following notions: definition of inertia, Sylvester's Law of Inertia, and Schur complements. For reference see [23], [24].

Definition 2.2.1. The inertia of an $n \times n$ symmetric matrix is an ordered triple

$$\text{In}(A) = (p(A), q(A), z(A)), \quad (2.55)$$

where $p(A), q(A), z(A)$ are, respectively, the number of positive, negative, and zero eigenvalues of A (including multiplicities).

Theorem 2.2.2 (Sylvester's Law of Inertia). *Consider two square matrices A and B that are symmetric. There exists an invertible matrix U such that $U^T A U = B$ if and only if $\text{In}(A) = \text{In}(B)$.*

Definition 2.2.2. Let M be a square matrix partitioned as

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} P & Q \\ R & S \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.56)$$

Assume that P is invertible. The Schur complement of P in the block matrix M is $S - R P^{-1} Q$.

Theorem 2.2.3. *Let M be a symmetric matrix such that it can be written in the following block matrix form:*

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} P & Q \\ Q^T & S \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.57)$$

where $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, S \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}, Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$. If P is invertible, then

$$\text{In}(M) = \text{In}(P) + \text{In}(S - Q^T P^{-1} Q) \quad (2.58)$$

Proof. Define a full rank matrix U as

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} I_{n \times n} & -P^{-1} Q \\ \mathbf{0}_{m \times n} & I_{m \times m} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.59)$$

The symmetry of M implies that P is symmetric as well. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} U^T M U &= \begin{pmatrix} I_{n \times n} & \mathbf{0}_{n \times m} \\ -Q^T P^{-1} & I_{m \times m} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} P & Q \\ Q^T & S \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_{n \times n} & -P^{-1} Q \\ \mathbf{0}_{m \times n} & I_{m \times m} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} P & \mathbf{0}_{n \times m} \\ \mathbf{0}_{m \times n} & S - Q^T P^{-1} Q \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.60)$$

By theorem 2.2.2 we get that $\text{In}(M) = \text{In}(U^T M U)$. Therefore, $\text{In}(M) = \text{In}(P) + \text{In}(S - Q^T P^{-1} Q)$. \square

Based on section 1.4 of [23], we can conclude the following consequence.

Corollary 2.2.4. *Let M be a symmetric matrix, which can be partitioned as in Theorem 2.2.3. Assume that P is invertible. Then, M is positive semidefinite if and only if P is positive definite and $S - Q^T P^{-1} Q$ is positive semidefinite.*

Proof. M is positive semidefinite if and only if $\text{In}(M) = (n + m - k, 0, k)$, where k is the multiplicity of eigenvalue zero. By assumption, P has only nonzero eigenvalues. In addition, by Theorem 2.2.3, $\text{In}(M) = \text{In}(P) + \text{In}(S - Q^T P^{-1} Q)$. Consequently, $\text{In}(M) = (n + m - k, 0, k)$ if and only if $\text{In}(P) = (n, 0, 0)$ and $\text{In}(S - Q^T P^{-1} Q) = (m - k, 0, k)$. \square

Next, we proceed with the proof of Lemma 2.2.1 (for reference see [10]).

Proof of Lemma 2.2.1. Define and factor the symmetric matrix M_i in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} M_i &= \begin{pmatrix} R_n & Q_i \\ Q_i & R_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T \Phi & \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T D_i \Phi \\ \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T D_i \Phi & \frac{1}{n} \Phi^T \Phi \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \Phi^T & \mathbf{0}_{n \times d}^T \\ \mathbf{0}_{n \times d}^T & \Phi^T \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{n} I_{n \times n} & \frac{1}{n} D_i \\ \frac{1}{n} D_i & \frac{1}{n} I_{n \times n} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Phi & \mathbf{0}_{n \times d} \\ \mathbf{0}_{n \times d} & \Phi \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.61)$$

where $\mathbf{0}_{n \times d}$ is the $n \times d$ zero matrix. Use the notation $G_n^T C_i G_n$ for the matrix product obtained in (2.61). First, we show that if C_i is positive semidefinite, then M_i is positive semidefinite too. Positive semidefiniteness of C_i means that $\forall y \in \mathbb{R}^{2n} \setminus \{\mathbf{0}_{2n \times 1}\}$ we have $y^T C_i y \geq 0$. Notice that G_n is a $2n \times 2d$ matrix, and $\text{rank}(G_n) = 2d$ due to assumption (II). Consequently, for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^{2d} \setminus \{\mathbf{0}_{2d \times 1}\}$ the vector $y = G_n x$ is not the zero vector, thus $x^T M_i x = (G_n x)^T C_i G_n x = y^T C_i y \geq 0$, i.e. M_i is positive semidefinite.

By corollary 2.2.4 $R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i$ is positive semidefinite if and only if M_i is positive semidefinite. Again, by corollary 2.2.4, we know that C_i is positive semidefinite if and only if $\frac{1}{n} I - \frac{1}{n} D_i D_i$ is positive semidefinite, but $D_i D_i = I$, so $\frac{1}{n} I - \frac{1}{n} D_i D_i = \mathbf{0}_{n \times n}$. Consequently, C_i is positive semidefinite, which implies that M_i is also positive semidefinite, equivalently, $R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i$ is positive semidefinite too. The whole argument holds regardless of $i \in [m - 1]$. \square

Introduce the following notations for the summands in the definition of $F_i(\theta)$ (2.54):

$$\begin{aligned} A_i &\doteq R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i \\ b_i &\doteq R_n \hat{\theta}_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} \eta_i \in \mathbb{R}^d \\ c_i &\doteq \hat{\theta}_n^T R_n \hat{\theta}_n - \eta_i^T R_n^{-1} \eta_i \in \mathbb{R}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.62)$$

Note that $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$, $b_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and $c_i \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proposition 2.2.5. *If $R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i$ is positive definite, then $\|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 - \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 = 0$ is an ellipsoid.*

Proof. We know from formula (2.54) that

$$F_i(\theta) = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 - \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 = \theta^T A_i \theta - 2\theta^T b_i + c_i. \quad (2.63)$$

A_i is a symmetric real matrix, as well as positive definite based on assumption. Hence, using spectral decomposition theorem (see [24]), it is orthogonally diagonalizable such that $U_i^T A_i U_i = \Lambda_i$, where Λ_i is a diagonal matrix ($\Lambda_i = \text{Diag}(\lambda_{i,1}, \dots, \lambda_{i,d})$) with eigenvalues of A_i (that are all nonnegative) as diagonal elements, and U_i is orthogonal. Define a new $1 \times n$ vector variable $\psi = U_i^T \theta$ (it is the linear combination of the coordinates of θ). Then apply $\theta = U_i \psi$ change of basis.

$$\begin{aligned}
\|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 - \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 &= \theta^T A_i \theta - 2\theta^T b_i + c_i = (U_i \psi)^T A_i U_i \psi - 2(U_i \psi)^T b_i + c_i \\
&= \psi^T \Lambda_i \psi - 2\psi^T w_i + c_i = c_i + \sum_{j=1}^d \left(\lambda_{i,j} \psi_j^2 - 2w_{i,j} \psi_j \right) \\
&= c_i - \sum_{j=1}^d \left(\frac{w_{i,j}}{\lambda_{i,j}} \right)^2 + \sum_{j=1}^d \lambda_{i,j} \left(\psi_j - \frac{w_{i,j}}{\lambda_{i,j}} \right)^2, \tag{2.64}
\end{aligned}$$

where $w_i = U_i^T b_i$. Note that we could transform the summands to full square since all the eigenvalues are positive by assumption. Let us introduce the notation $d_i = c_i - \sum_{j=1}^d \left(\frac{w_{i,j}}{\lambda_{i,j}} \right)^2$. Then, based on the value of d_i , we either get an ellipsoid or a degenerate ellipsoid.

- If $d_i = 0$, then $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : F_i(\theta) = 0\}$ contains a single point (degenerate case).
- If $d_i < 0$, then $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : F_i(\theta) = 0\} = \emptyset$ (degenerate case).
- If $d_i > 0$, then $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : F_i(\theta) = 0\}$ determines a d -dimensional ellipsoid.

□

Remark 2.2.4. The next example shows that it is possible that $R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i$ is singular, which implies that $F_i(\theta) = 0$ is not an ellipse. Choose $\varphi_1 = \varphi_3 = (1, 0)^T$, $\varphi_2 = (0, 1)^T$ (i.e. $n = 3$, and $\Phi = (\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3)^T$ is a 2×3 matrix) so $\Phi^T \Phi = \text{Diag}(2, 1)$. In addition, if $D_i = \text{Diag}(1, 1, -1)$, then $F(\theta) = \frac{2}{3} (\theta_1^2 - \theta_1(Y_1 + Y_3) + Y_1 Y_3)$. Therefore, $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^2 : F(\theta) = 0\}$ is either empty or determines one or two lines.

In what follows, we finally state the main theorem that describes the shape of SPS confidence regions [10]. Recall the definition of star convexity.

Definition 2.2.3. A set $A \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is star convex if $\exists a^* \in A$ such that $\forall a \in A, \forall \lambda \in [0, 1]$ $\lambda a + (1 - \lambda)a^* \in A$, where a^* is called star center of A .

Remark 2.2.5. If $A \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is convex, then it is star convex with any $a \in A$ as star center.

Theorem 2.2.6. *If assumption (I) and assumption (II) hold, and $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is nonempty, then $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is star convex with the least-squares estimate $\hat{\theta}_n$ as the star center.*

Sketch of proof. Use the notation $F_i(\theta) = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 - \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2$. We know that

$$\hat{\Theta}_n = \bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=q}} \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 \prec_\pi \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}. \quad (2.65)$$

The set $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 \prec_\pi \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}$ is either $\mathcal{E}_i \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : F_i(\theta) \leq 0\}$ or $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_i \doteq \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : F_i(\theta) < 0\}$ based on the particular π .

The Hessian of the quadratic form $F_i(\theta)$ is $2(R_n - Q_i R_n^{-1} Q_i)$, which is positive semidefinite according to Lemma 2.2.1, hence $F_i(\theta)$ is convex function, and $\mathcal{E}_i, \bar{\mathcal{E}}_i$ are convex sets. It can be shown, that if $\mathcal{E}_i \neq \emptyset$, then $\hat{\theta}_n \in \mathcal{E}_i$, as well as $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_i \neq \emptyset$ implies $\hat{\theta}_n \in \bar{\mathcal{E}}_i$. Thus, $\bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 \prec_\pi \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2\}$ is the intersection of convex or empty sets, and if it is not empty, then it contains the LSE. Therefore, if $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is nonempty, then it is the union of intersection of star convex sets with the same star center $\hat{\theta}_n$, thus $\hat{\Theta}_n$ is star convex itself. \square

Determination of the exact SPS confidence region would require finding the roots of $\|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2 - \|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2$, which in general means that one needs to solve quadratic equations to obtain the boundary of the set. As a final thought regarding the shape of SPS regions, we mention that there exists an ellipsoidal outer approximation of $\hat{\Theta}_n$ using convex programming [10], which provide a solution for the computation demanding problem of calculating the boundaries of the SPS confidence regions. The detailed discussion is omitted from this thesis due to the fact that we intend to use SPS method in one dimension, where there is feasible approach to describe the confidence set explicitly as an interval.

2.2.3 Strong consistency of the SPS method

During the construction of SPS confidence region there were no assumptions made on the moments of the noise sequence $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$. In what follows, based on [11], we give a short-spoken insight about what is required to keep SPS regions within an arbitrary small, d -dimensional norm-ball.

Definition 2.2.4. Let $(\mathbb{R}^d, \|\cdot\|)$ be a d -dimensional real vector space equipped with a norm. Then $B_\varepsilon(\theta^*) = \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \|\theta - \theta^*\| \leq \varepsilon\}$ is the closed norm-ball with radius ε centered at θ^* .

Besides (I), (II) we consider the following assumptions:

(III) The sequence of positive definite matrices $(R_n)_{n=1}^\infty$ converges to a positive definite matrix R :

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} R_n = R. \quad (2.66)$$

(IV) The growth rate of the regressors is restricted:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{\|\varphi_t\|^4}{t^2} < \infty. \quad (2.67)$$

(V) The second moments of the noises grow in a limited rate:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{\mathbb{E}[N_t^2]^2}{t^2} < \infty. \quad (2.68)$$

Now, we state the theorem regarding the size of $\hat{\Theta}_n$, which property is called strong consistency. The proof can be found in [11].

Theorem 2.2.7. *If (I), (II), (III), (IV), (V) hold, then $\forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall n \geq N \hat{\Theta}_n \subseteq B_\varepsilon(\theta^*)$ with probability 1.*

Remark 2.2.6. The threshold index N in 2.2.7 is stochastic in the sense that it depends on the realization of $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$ noise sequence. Furthermore, Theorem 2.2.7 does not restrict the possibility that the second moments of the noises may grow to infinity, even so the confidence regions remain in an arbitrary small norm-ball asymptotically.

2.2.4 Generalization of the SPS method

The thoroughly analyzed SPS finite-sample confidence region construction method can be modified in certain ways such that we get a more general approach, and the inclusion of the true parameter θ^* is still guaranteed with user-chosen, rational probability $1 - q/m$. We prove that the sign-perturbation can be relaxed to symmetric perturbation. In addition, we consider the alternatives of ranking the perturbed sums.

We assume the same sampling mechanism as in Section 2.1. Define the reference sum in case of $i = 0$ and the perturbed sums for $i \in [m - 1]$ as

$$M_0(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t |\rho_{0,t}| (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta), \quad (2.69)$$

$$M_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \rho_{i,t} (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta), \quad (2.70)$$

where $(\rho_{i,t})_{i=0,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ are independent identically distributed random variables that are symmetric about zero. In addition, we require that $\mathbb{P}(\rho_{i,t} = 0) = 0$ for all $i \in [m-1], t \in [n]$. We also assume that each element of $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$ and $(\rho_{i,t})_{t=0}^n$ are independent for every $i \in [m-1] \cup \{0\}$. We refer to the random sums $(M_i(\theta))_{i=1}^{m-1}$ as symmetrically-perturbed sums (SymPS).

The confidence region construction algorithm is defined similarly as in the sign-perturbation case. First the global variables are set by SymPS-initialization (Algorithm 5). Then the modified indicator procedure is defined in Algorithm 6. We also allow the usage of not only the Euclidean norm but any continuous function $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (for which $\text{Dom } f = \mathbb{R}^d$) to map the symmetrically-perturbed sums (which are vectors) to the set of real numbers. The rank of the reference value, and \prec_π strict total order are defined similarly as in the sign-perturbation case (see Section 2.1).

Algorithm 5 (SymPS-initialization)

1. Set probability level $p = 1 - q/m$, where $q, m \in \mathbb{Z}^+ : m > q > 0$.
 2. Let $R_n = \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \varphi_t^\top$, factor R_n such that $R_n = R_n^{1/2} R_n^{1/2}$.
 3. Generate nm independent and identically distributed random variables $(\rho_{i,t})_{i=0,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ that are symmetric about the origin, where $\mathbb{P}(\rho_{i,t} = 0) = 0$.
 4. Generate a π permutation on $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$ uniformly.
 5. Define \prec_π strict total order on any m real numbers z_0, \dots, z_{m-1} such that $z_i \prec_\pi z_j$ if and only if $(z_i < z_j)$ or $(z_i = z_j, \text{ but } \pi(i) < \pi(j))$.
-

Algorithm 6 (SymPS-indicator(θ))

1. For input vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m-1\}$ let

$$M_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \rho_{i,t} (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta),$$

$$M_0(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t |\rho_{0,t}| (Y_t - \varphi_t^\top \theta).$$

2. Sort $f(M_0(\theta)), f(M_1(\theta)), \dots, f(M_{m-1}(\theta))$ scalars in ascending order according to \prec_π . Let $\mathcal{R}_0(\theta)$ denote the rank of the reference value $f(M_0(\theta))$ in the ordering.
 3. If $\mathcal{R}_0(\theta) \leq m - q$ return 1, else return 0.
-

Define the SymPS based confidence set as

$$\bar{\Theta}_n = \{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d : \text{SymPS-indicator}(\theta) = 1\}. \quad (2.71)$$

Theorem 2.2.8. *If assumptions (I) and (II) are satisfied, then*

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \bar{\Theta}_n) = 1 - \frac{q}{m}. \quad (2.72)$$

Proof of Theorem 2.2.8. The reasoning goes similarly as in the proof of the exact con-

fidence level of $\hat{\Theta}_n$ (see proof of Theorem 2.1.2). We highlight the parts where it differs. By definition

$$M_0(\theta^*) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t |\rho_{0,t}| N_t, \quad (2.73)$$

$$M_i(\theta^*) = \frac{1}{n} R_n^{-1/2} \sum_{t=1}^n \varphi_t \rho_{i,t} N_t, \quad (2.74)$$

thus $M_0(\theta^*)$ is the function of the noises and the absolute value of the symmetric perturbation variables $(|\rho_{0,t}|)_{t=1}^n$.

$$S(|\rho_{0,1}|N_1, \dots, |\rho_{0,n}|N_n) \doteq M_0(\theta^*). \quad (2.75)$$

Furthermore, each $M_i(\theta^*)$ ($i \in [m-1]$) depends on the corresponding symmetrically-perturbed noises $(\rho_{i,t}N_t)_{t=1}^n$, via the same function $S(\cdot)$.

$$S(\rho_{i,1}N_1, \dots, \rho_{i,n}N_n) \doteq M_i(\theta^*). \quad (2.76)$$

We know that $(\rho_{i,t})_{i=0,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ and $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$ are collectively independent by definition. By assumption (I), $\mathbb{P}(\rho_{i,t} = 0) = \mathbb{P}(N_t = 0) = 0$, and N_t and $\rho_{i,t}$ are symmetric about the origin. Therefore, we can use Lemma 2.1.1 to deduce that for all $t \in [n]$ the random variables $|N_t|$, $\text{sgn}(N_t)$, $|\rho_{i,t}|$, and $\text{sgn}(\rho_{i,t})$ are independent. Define random variables $\gamma_{i,t} \doteq \text{sgn}(N_t) \text{sgn}(\rho_{i,t})$, $\gamma_{0,t} \doteq \text{sgn}(N_t)$. According to Lemma 2.1.3, $(\gamma_{i,t})_{i=0,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ are independent and identically distributed Rademacher random variables. Let us introduce the random variables $\kappa_{i,t} \doteq \gamma_{i,t} \cdot |\rho_{i,t}|$ (i.e. $\kappa_{0,t} = \text{sgn}(N_t)|\rho_{0,t}|$). Using the properties stated above, we get that $(\kappa_{i,t})_{i=0,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ are also i.i.d. random variables, namely they follow the same distribution as the elements of $(\rho_{i,t})_{i=0,t=1}^{m-1,n}$. Fix the value of $|N_t| = v_t$ for every $t \in [n]$, and define the random variables

$$Z_i(v_1, \dots, v_n, \kappa_{i,1}, \dots, \kappa_{i,n}) \doteq f(S(\kappa_{i,1}v_1, \dots, \kappa_{i,n}v_n)) \quad (2.77)$$

for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$. These are independent and identically distributed, since f is continuous, and $S(\cdot)$ is measurable, thus $f \circ S$ is also measurable, and a measurable function applied to each element of an i.i.d. sequence $((\kappa_{i,1}, \dots, \kappa_{i,n}))_{i=0}^{m-1}$ yields independent and identically distributed variables (namely $(Z_i)_{i=0}^{m-1}$ are i.i.d.). Thus by Lemma 2.1.5, the $(Z_i(v_1, \dots, v_n, \kappa_{i,1}, \dots, \kappa_{i,n}))_{i=0}^{m-1}$ sample is uniformly ordered with respect to \prec_π , which means that each order of the sequence appears with probability $1/m!$. This exact probability holds for any realization of $(|N_t|)_{t=1}^n$, thus using Lemma 2.1.4 concludes the proof. \square

Remark 2.2.7. In the construction of $\bar{\Theta}_n$ the requirement that the rank of $f(M_0(\theta))$ is

at most $m - q$ can be relaxed. Fix any $m - q$ positions $\mathcal{M} \subseteq [m], |\mathcal{M}| = m - q$ in the ranking. If $R_0(\theta) \in \mathcal{M}$, i.e $M_0(\theta)$ takes one place out of the $m - q$ predetermined positions, then the inclusion of the unknown parameter in the confidence set still holds with probability $1 - q/m$ due to uniform ordering. Although this modification can be done, it may not be practically useful since it can produce disconnected confidence set. However, in the final part of the thesis, we will use this property to modified the SPS method.

Remark 2.2.8. Increasing m and q simultaneously while maintaining a fixed rational confidence level p (that they define) does not provide significant advantage from a practical point of view [10].

Remark 2.2.9. If not stated otherwise, when we talk about SymPS we consider f to be the square of the Euclidean norm in the following parts of the thesis.

Originally, we intended to modify SPS in a way that we can avoid the event that the SPS confidence region becomes the whole space, consequently, it becomes unbounded. This lead to the idea of symmetric-perturbation. Although continuous symmetric-perturbation helps to avoid the event that $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 \equiv \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$, but a new problem arises. Namely, it becomes possible that the inequality $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 > \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$ holds in an unbounded set that is not even connected. This ruins star convexity. For example, consider $n = d = q = 1, m = 2, \varphi_1 = 1$, and continuous symmetric perturbation. In this case, if $|\rho_{0,1}| < \rho_{1,1}$, then the SymPS confidence set $\bar{\Theta}_n$ might be the union of two semi-infinite sets that are disjoint.

Chapter 3

Perturbation based UCB policy

We saw that sign-perturbed sums method provides non-asymptotic confidence set that includes the unknown parameter of the linear regression model with exact (user-chosen) probability. If the SPS confidence regions are intervals, then one can use them to construct an upper confidence bound algorithm for decision making in multi-armed bandit environment. In this final section of the thesis, we give further analysis of the SPS method in one dimension, and we introduce the concept of linear SPS. After that, we propose a new stochastic MAB algorithm for symmetric environments. We conclude the thesis by comparing the proposed algorithm with asymptotically optimal UCB.

3.1 Sign-perturbed Sums in one dimension

We consider a one-dimensional linear sampling mechanism $Y_t = \varphi_t \theta^* + N_t$, where $\theta^* \in \mathbb{R}$ is the unknown system parameter. We also assume that $\varphi_t = 1$ for every $t \in [n]$. This means that $Y_t = \theta^* + N_t$, so in each time instance the random variable Y_t is symmetric about θ^* under assumption (I). The reference sum is defined as $S_0(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \theta)$, and the sign-perturbed sums become $S_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \theta)$ for $i \in [m-1]$, where $(\alpha_{i,t})_{i=1,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ are independent Rademacher random variables. Furthermore,

$$S_0(\theta)^2 = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \theta) \right)^2 = (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^2, \quad (3.1)$$

$$S_i(\theta)^2 = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \theta) \right)^2 = \left(\theta \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \right) - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t \right)^2, \quad (3.2)$$

where $\hat{\theta}_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n Y_t$ is the least-squares estimate. Later, we will use the fact that if $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \neq 0$, then

$$S_i(\theta)^2 = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} (\theta - \hat{\theta}_{i,n}) \right)^2, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\hat{\theta}_{i,n} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}}$.

By construction

$$\hat{\Theta}_n = \bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=q}} \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : |S_0(\theta)|^2 \prec_{\pi} |S_i(\theta)|^2\}. \quad (3.4)$$

Similarly as in the general case $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : |S_0(\theta)|^2 \prec_{\pi} |S_i(\theta)|^2\}$ is either $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : |S_0(\theta)|^2 - |S_i(\theta)|^2 \leq 0\}$ or $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : |S_0(\theta)|^2 - |S_i(\theta)|^2 < 0\}$ depending on the underlying permutation π . Notice that the functions $|S_i(\theta)|^2 = S_i(\theta)^2$ and $|S_0(\theta)|^2 = S_0(\theta)^2$ determine nonnegative parabolas, thus we refer to $S_i(\theta)^2$ as perturbed parabola, and $S_0(\theta)^2$ is called the reference parabola.

3.1.1 Properties of the SPS parabolas and their intersections

Before showing how one can determine the exact SPS confidence regions in one dimension constructively, we thoroughly analyze the properties of the defined parabolas and their intersections.

First we get the roots of the parabolas in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} S_i(\theta)^2 = 0 &\iff \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \theta) = 0 \\ &\iff \theta = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t}{\sum_{l=1}^n \alpha_{i,l}} = \hat{\theta}_{i,n} \text{ and } \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \neq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

$$S_0(\theta)^2 = 0 \iff \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \theta) = 0 \iff \theta = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n Y_t = \hat{\theta}_n. \quad (3.6)$$

This also shows that $S_i(\theta)^2$ may not have a root. When $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} = 0$, the reference parabola becomes a horizontal line but this phenomenon can only occur if n is even. Also note that the horizontal line may be $y = 0$.

Remark 3.1.1. Let f, g be two functions for which $\text{Dom}(f) = \text{Dom}(g)$. We use the notation $f \equiv g$, if $\forall \theta \in \text{Dom}(f) : f(\theta) = g(\theta)$. In addition, the notation $f \not\equiv g$ is used, when $\exists \theta \in \text{Dom}(f) : f(\theta) \neq g(\theta)$.

Now examine when $F_i(\theta) \doteq S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2 = 0$ is satisfied ($i \in [m-1]$, $S_0(\theta)^2 \not\equiv$

$S_i(\theta)^2$). If both $S_0(\theta)$ and $S_i(\theta)$ are positive or nonnegative, then

$$\begin{aligned}
S_0(\theta) &= S_i(\theta) \\
\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \theta) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \theta) \\
0 &= \sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1) (Y_t - \theta) \\
\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1) \theta &= \sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1) Y_t \\
\theta &= \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1) Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1)}. \tag{3.7}
\end{aligned}$$

If $S_0(\theta)$ is negative, and $S_i(\theta)$ is nonnegative, or vice versa, then $S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2 = 0$ is satisfied exactly when $S_0(\theta) = -S_i(\theta)$. The solution in θ is

$$\theta = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} + 1) Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} + 1)}. \tag{3.8}$$

Introduce the notation $\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}$ for the two intersection points of the reference and the i^{th} perturbed parabola:

$$\theta_{i,1} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1) Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} - 1)}, \tag{3.9}$$

$$\theta_{i,2} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} + 1) Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n (\alpha_{i,t} + 1)}, \tag{3.10}$$

which are well defined when $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ is not constant $+1$ or -1 sequence (recall that we use the notation $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n \neq \pm \mathbf{1}$ in this case).

Lemma 3.1.1 (One unique intersection). *Assume that $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$. Then $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$ if and only if $\hat{\theta}_n = \hat{\theta}_{i,n}$ or $S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv 0$. Furthermore, if $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$ then they equal to $\hat{\theta}_n$.*

Proof. $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$ means that

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{-\sum_{t=1}^n Y_t + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t}{-n + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}} &= \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n Y_t + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t}{n + \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}} \\
n \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t - \left(\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \right) \left(\sum_{t=1}^n Y_t \right) &= -n \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t + \left(\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \right) \left(\sum_{t=1}^n Y_t \right) \\
\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t &= \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \right) \left(\sum_{t=1}^n Y_t \right). \tag{3.11}
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, if $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} = 0$, then $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t = 0$, thus $S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv 0$. If $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \neq 0$,

then (3.11) can be written as

$$\hat{\theta}_{i,n} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n Y_t = \hat{\theta}_n, \quad (3.12)$$

which concludes the first part of the lemma. Furthermore, according to (3.12), $S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = S_i(\hat{\theta}_{i,n})^2 = 0$, but $S_0(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0$ as well, thus $\theta_{i,1}$ and $\theta_{i,2}$ cannot be other than $\hat{\theta}_n$. \square

Lemma 3.1.1 states that if $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$, then $\hat{\theta}_n$ is surely the only root of $S_i(\theta)^2$, and vice versa (assuming that $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$).

Corollary 3.1.2. *If $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$ and $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$, then $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : S_0(\theta)^2 \leq S_i(\theta)^2\} = \{\hat{\theta}_n\}$ and $S_i(\theta) < S_0(\theta)$ for $\theta \neq \hat{\theta}_n$.*

Proof. If $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$ then $S_0(\theta)^2 = S_i(\theta)^2$ if and only if $\theta = \hat{\theta}_n$. Furthermore, the inequality $S_0(\theta)^2 < S_i(\theta)^2$ is never satisfied for $\theta \neq \hat{\theta}_n$, since

$$S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2 = \begin{cases} S_0(\theta)^2 & , \text{ if } S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv 0 \\ \left(1 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}\right)^2\right) (\theta - \hat{\theta}_n)^2 & , \text{ if } S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.13)$$

Therefore, $S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2 > 0$ for $\theta \neq \hat{\theta}_n$, since the only root of $S_0(\theta)^2$ is $\hat{\theta}_n$. \square

Lemma 3.1.3 (Equivalent parabolas). *$S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2$ if and only if $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ is constant -1 or $+1$ sequence.*

Proof. We saw in $d \in \mathbb{N}^+$ dimension that $\|S_i(\theta)\|_2^2 = \|S_0(\theta)\|_2^2$ if $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ (regardless of the regressors and $(Y_t)_{t=1}^n$). On the other hand, if $S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2$, then either $S_i(\theta) \equiv S_0(\theta)$ or $S_i(\theta) \equiv -S_0(\theta)$. Therefore, either $1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}$ or $-1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}$, since the coefficient of θ in $S_i(\theta)$ and in $S_0(\theta)$ must match to the extent of sign. Consequently, $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$. \square

Lemma 3.1.4. *$F_i(\theta) = S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2$ is a strictly convex parabola if $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$.*

Proof. Strict convexity of $F_i(\theta)$ follows from

$$\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2} [S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2] = 2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}\right) > 0, \quad (3.14)$$

since $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n \neq \pm \mathbf{1} \iff S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$ (see Lemma 3.1.3). It is a parabola because the coefficient of θ^2 is $1 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}\right)^2 \neq 0$. \square

Lemma 3.1.5 (Two unique intersections). *Assume that $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$, and $\theta_{i,1} \neq \theta_{i,2}$. Let $\theta_{i,L} = \min\{\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}\}$, $\theta_{i,R} = \max\{\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}\}$. Then $\theta_{i,L} < \hat{\theta}_n < \theta_{i,R}$ and*

$$S_i(\theta)^2 < S_0(\theta)^2 \text{ if } \theta \in (-\infty, \theta_{i,L}) \cup (\theta_{i,R}, \infty), \quad (3.15)$$

$$S_i(\theta)^2 > S_0(\theta)^2 \text{ if } \theta \in (\theta_{i,L}, \theta_{i,R}). \quad (3.16)$$

Proof. If $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} = 0$, then $S_i(\theta)^2$ is a horizontal line, but $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv 0$ due to Lemma 3.1.1. Otherwise, $S_i(\theta)^2$ has a single root $\hat{\theta}_{i,n} \neq \hat{\theta}_n$ due to the assumptions (follows from Lemma 3.1.1 and $\theta_{i,1} \neq \theta_{i,2}$ condition). Either way $F_i(\hat{\theta}_n) = S_0(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 - S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = -S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 < 0$. Furthermore, $F_i(\theta)$ is strictly convex parabola (see Lemma 3.1.4), thus $F_i(\theta)$ has one root left to $\hat{\theta}_n$ and one to the right. \square

Table 3.1 provides a summary of the previously achieved results regarding the intersections, and shows the relation system of a perturbed and the reference parabola given the exact number of intersections.

Infinitely many intersections	One intersection	Two intersections
$S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2$ $\iff (\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$.	$\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2} = \hat{\theta}_n$, $S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = S_0(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0$, $S_i(\theta)^2 < S_0(\theta)^2$ if $\theta \neq \hat{\theta}_n$.	$S_i(\theta)^2 > S_0(\theta)^2$ if $\theta \in (\theta_{i,L}, \theta_{i,R})$. $S_i(\theta)^2 < S_0(\theta)^2$ if $\theta \in \mathbb{R} \setminus [\theta_{i,L}, \theta_{i,R}]$.

Table 3.1: Classification of intersections

3.1.2 Infinite or empty intervals

Before showing the constructive SPS confidence region determination algorithm, we review the case of infinite or empty intervals in one dimension assuming specific regressors.

Proposition 3.1.6 (Infinite regions in 1D). *If $(\varphi_t)_{t=1}^n = \mathbf{1}$, then in one dimension*

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}) = \sum_{k=q}^{m-1} p(m, k, n) \sum_{h=q}^k P(m, k-h, h), \quad (3.17)$$

where $p(m, k, n)$ and $P(m, l, h)$ are defined in (2.43) and (2.47) respectively.

Proof. A necessary condition for $\{\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}\}$ to occur is that there exists $i \in [m-1]$ such that $\mathcal{E}_i = \{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : S_0(\theta)^2 \prec_{\pi} S_i(\theta)^2\}$ is not bounded. If $S_0(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_i(\theta)^2$, then $S_0(\theta)^2$ and $S_i(\theta)^2$ have either one or two intersections. By Lemma 3.1.1 (more precisely because of Corollary 3.1.2), in case of one intersection, we get

$$\mathcal{E}_i = \begin{cases} \{\hat{\theta}_n\}, & \text{if } \pi(0) < \pi(i), \\ \emptyset, & \text{if } \pi(0) > \pi(i). \end{cases} \quad (3.18)$$

By Lemma 3.1.5, in case of two unique intersections $\theta_{i,1} \neq \theta_{i,2}$, we know that \mathcal{E}_i is bounded, i.e. $\mathcal{E}_i \subseteq [\min\{\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}\}, \max\{\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}\}]$. Thereby, \mathcal{E}_i is bounded either way. Moreover, finite union of bounded sets is also bounded, thus $\{\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}\}$ cannot occur

when $S_0(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_i(\theta)^2$. On the other hand, if $S_0(\theta)^2 \equiv S_i(\theta)^2$, then $\{\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}\}$ occurs with probability $Q \doteq \sum_{k=q}^{m-1} p(m, k, n) \sum_{h=q}^k P(m, k-h, h)$ due to the fact that $S_0(\theta)^2 \equiv S_i(\theta)^2 \iff (\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ by Lemma 3.1.3 (Q is the probability of the event that $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ for at least q perturbed parabolas and $\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}$ happen at the same time based on (2.48)). \square

Remark 3.1.2. Notice that the equation $\hat{\theta}_n = \hat{\theta}_{i,n}$ holds when $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ (consequently, $S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = S_0(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0$), but the equality can happen in other cases too. For example, if $\alpha_{i,1} = \alpha_{i,2} = 1, \alpha_{i,3} = -1$ and $Y_1 = Y_2 = Y_3 = 1$.

We saw that in case of one-dimensional SPS and constant 1 regressors, we can determine exactly the probability of the occurrence of infinite confidence intervals. Nevertheless, the probability of empty confidence sets cannot be determined exactly without further assumption on the noise sequence.

Proposition 3.1.7 (Empty regions in 1D). *If $(\varphi_t)_{t=1}^n = \mathbf{1}$, then in one dimension*

$$\mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{I}_u| \geq m - q) \leq \mathbb{P}(\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset) = \mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{L}_u| \geq m - q), \quad (3.19)$$

where $\mathcal{I}_u = \{i : S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\}$ and $\mathcal{L}_u = \{i : S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\}$.

Remark 3.1.3. The lower index in \mathcal{I}_u and \mathcal{L}_u suggest that the perturbed parabolas, index by these sets, always stay "under" the reference parabola regardless of θ .

Proof of Proposition 3.1.7. By the definition, $\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset$ if and only if there are at least $m - q$ index $i \in [m - 1]$ such that for every $\forall \theta \in \mathbb{R}$ $S_i(\theta)^2 \prec_{\pi} S_0(\theta)^2$. We examine when $A_i \doteq \{\forall \theta \in \mathbb{R} S_i(\theta)^2 \prec_{\pi} S_0(\theta)^2\}$ event can happen based on the number of intersections between $S_i(\theta)^2$ and $S_0(\theta)^2$. By using Table 3.1, we can distinguish the following cases.

- The probability of no intersections is 0. Therefore $\forall \theta \in \mathbb{R} S_i(\theta)^2 < S_0(\theta)^2$ is never satisfied (case of no intersection).
- If $S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2$, then A_i happens only if $\pi(i) < \pi(0)$. (case of infinite number of intersections).
- If there is only one intersection, then A_i occurs only if $\pi(i) < \pi(0)$ (case of one intersection).
- If $\theta_{i,1} \neq \theta_{i,2}$, then A_i can never be true, since $S_i(\theta)^2 > S_0(\theta)^2$ between the two intersections (case of two intersections).

There is one or infinitely many intersections if and only if $S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0$. Furthermore, based on the four cases above, A_i occurs if and only if there are infinitely many intersections or just one and in both cases $\pi(i) < \pi(0)$ must be true. Putting everything together we get that $A_i = \{S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\}$. In addition, $\mathcal{I}_u \subseteq \mathcal{L}_u$, which concludes the proof. \square

Corollary 3.1.8. *If Y_1, \dots, Y_n are continuous random variables, then*

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset) = \mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{I}_u| \geq m - q). \quad (3.20)$$

Proof. It is satisfactory to show that $\mathcal{I}_u = \mathcal{L}_u$ almost surely. This is the case indeed when $B_i \doteq \{i : S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2, S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\}$ is empty with probability one. We show that even $C_i \doteq \{i : S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2, S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0\}$ is empty ($B_i \subseteq C_i$).

Let us denote the root of $S_i(\theta)^2$ by $\hat{\theta}_{i,n}$ (if it exists). Consider a perturbed parabola that satisfies both $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2$ and $S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0$. We know that Y_1, \dots, Y_n are continuous, thus $S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv 0$ almost surely. Consequently, $S_i(\theta)^2$ intersects the reference parabola in a single point $\hat{\theta}_n$, which is the only root of $S_i(\theta)^2$ (see Lemma 3.1.1), so $\hat{\theta}_n = \hat{\theta}_{i,n}$. However,

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\theta}_n = \hat{\theta}_{i,n}) = \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n Y_t = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t}}\right) = 0, \quad (3.21)$$

since for every realization of $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n \neq \pm \mathbf{1}$ we get zero probability, thus the unconditional probability is equal to 0 as well (see Lemma 2.1.4). \square

Remark 3.1.4. In the previous section we proved in general (i.e. in \mathbb{R}^d , and for arbitrary $(\varphi_t)_{t=1}^n$ regressor sequence which satisfies (II)) that

$$\mathbb{P}(\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset) \geq \mathbb{P}(|\mathcal{I}_u| \geq m - q) = \sum_{k=m-q}^{m-1} p(m, k, n) \sum_{l=m-q}^k P(m, l, k - l). \quad (3.22)$$

3.1.3 Constructive determination of the one-dimensional SPS confidence regions

If θ goes through the real line \mathbb{R} (from $-\infty$ to ∞), then the rank of $S_0(\theta)^2$ (denoted by $R_0(\theta)$) in the ascending order of $\{S_i(\theta)^2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ according to \prec_π changes only if a perturbed parabola $S_i(\theta)^2$ intersects $S_0(\theta)^2$. Since the SPS confidence sets are star convex, consequently, they are connected intervals, it is sufficient to determine only the infimum and supremum of the set to characterize the whole interval. Introduce the following sets:

$$\mathcal{I}_a \doteq \{i : S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2, \pi(i) > \pi(0)\} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\mathcal{I}_u \doteq \{i : S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\} \quad (3.24)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_u \doteq \{i : S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0, S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\} \quad (3.25)$$

\mathcal{I}_a and $\mathcal{I}_U \cup \mathcal{H}_u$ are the index sets of all perturbed parabolas that are, respectively, always (for every $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$) "above" and "under" $S_0(\theta)$ according \prec_π . Using this notation

$$|\mathcal{I}_u \cup \mathcal{H}_u| = |\mathcal{I}_u| \cup |\mathcal{H}_u| < R_0(\theta) \leq m - |\mathcal{I}_a| \quad (3.26)$$

regardless of θ .

Define $\mathcal{O} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{m-1} \{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : S_i(\theta)^2 = S_0(\theta)^2, S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2\}$ the set of all occurring intersections ($k \doteq |\mathcal{O}| \leq 2(m-1)$) ignoring perturbed parabolas that are equivalent to $S_0(\theta)$ (i.e. every set in the definition of \mathcal{O} contains either one or two elements, for reminder see Table 3.1). Sort the elements of \mathcal{O} in ascending order: $-\infty < \theta_1 < \theta_2 < \dots < \theta_k < \infty$, and define $\theta_0 = -\infty, \theta_{k+1} = \infty$. Introduce $k_j \doteq |\{i : S_i(\theta_j)^2 = 0, S_i(\theta)^2 \not\equiv S_0(\theta)^2\}|$, i.e. it is the number of perturbed parabolas (not equivalent to $S_0(\theta)$) that intersects the reference parabola in θ_j . Then $R_0(\xi) = R_0(\psi) + k_j$ for $\theta_j < \hat{\theta}_n, \xi \in (\theta_{j-1}, \theta_j)$ and $\psi \in (\theta_j, \theta_{j+1})$ due to Lemma 3.1.5. Note that it is impossible that two different perturbed parabolas (that are not equivalent to $S_0(\theta)^2$) intersect the reference parabola in the same $\theta_l \neq \hat{\theta}_n$ point and one of them gets "under" and the other goes "above" $S_0(\theta)^2$ due to the strict convexity of $F_i(\theta) = S_0(\theta)^2 - S_i(\theta)^2$ (see Lemma 3.1.4). Similarly $R_0(\xi) = R_0(\psi) - k_j$ for $\theta_j > \hat{\theta}_n, \xi \in (\theta_{j-1}, \theta_j)$ and $\psi \in (\theta_j, \theta_{j+1})$. Also consider that it is not possible that $R_0(\theta) > m - q$ (or $R_0(\theta) \leq m - q$) for every $\theta < \hat{\theta}_n$, but $R_0(\theta) \leq m - q$ (or $R_0(\theta) > m - q$) for all $\theta > \hat{\theta}_n$, since the number of intersections that are strictly left to the LSE equals to the number of intersections that are strictly right to LSE (see Lemma 3.1.5).

Using all the observations above, if we take the partition of \mathbb{R} by the intersections, then we get $\mathbb{R} = \mathcal{O} \cup \bigcup_{l=0}^k (\theta_l, \theta_{l+1})$, and starting from θ_1 and going towards $\hat{\theta}_n$ the value $R_0(\theta)$ decreases between the intervals (between (θ_{j-1}, θ_j) and (θ_j, θ_{j+1}) the decrease is exactly k_j) until we reach the intersection closest to $\hat{\theta}_n$ from the left. This means that when we reach the first interval (θ_h, θ_{h+1}) (where $\theta_h < \hat{\theta}_n$) for which $R_0(\theta) \leq m - q \forall \theta \in (\theta_h, \theta_{h+1})$, then we surely know that $R_0(\theta) \leq m - q \forall \theta \in (\theta_h, \hat{\theta}_n)$. Similarly, consider the intervals from right to left starting with $(\theta_k, \theta_{k+1}) = (\theta_k, \infty)$ up until we reach $\hat{\theta}_n$. If the first interval for which $R_0(\theta) \leq m - q$ is (θ_{g-1}, θ_g) , then $R_0(\theta) \leq m - q \forall \theta \in (\hat{\theta}_n, \theta_g)$. Obviously, it is possible that θ_h does not exist but if and only if θ_g does not exist either (due to the fact that $\forall \theta \in (-\infty, \hat{\theta}_n) R_0(\theta) \geq z \iff \forall \theta \in (\hat{\theta}_n, \infty) R_0(\theta) \geq z$). If that is the case, then the confidence set is either a single point, or \emptyset . Also it may be possible that $\theta_h = -\infty$ but if and only if $\theta_g = \infty$. Therefore, when neither the empty nor the single point case occurs, then $\hat{\Theta}_n \in \{(\theta_h, \theta_g), [\theta_h, \theta_g], (\theta_h, \theta_g], [\theta_h, \theta_g]\}$ based on the value $\pi(0)$. On the other hand, if θ_h, θ_g do not exist, then we have to calculate $R_0(\hat{\theta}_n)$ to decide between empty set and $\{\hat{\theta}_n\}$ cases.

Finally, using all the facts above, we can introduce the constructive SPS confidence determination algorithm in one dimension using constant 1 regressors (see Algorithm 7). Notice that in Algorithm 7 we have $\mathcal{L}_u = \mathcal{I}_u \cup \mathcal{H}_u$. In addition, R corresponds to

the value $R_0(\theta)$ in the examined interval, therefore the initial value of R is correctly set, since for every $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ $R_0(\theta) \leq m - |\mathcal{I}_a|$ (recall that $R_0(\theta)$ is the rank of $S_0(\theta)^2$ in the ascending order of $\{S_i(\theta)^2\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ according to \prec_π). Furthermore, if both L and E variables remains $\hat{\theta}_n$ after the two loops in the algorithm, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \{\hat{\theta}_n\}$, i.e. it cannot be empty since at that point in the algorithm we already considered the case when $|\mathcal{L}_u| \geq m - q$, which is the only way to get empty set. The four cases in the last point of Algorithm 7 matters only in case of discrete noise.

Remark 3.1.5. We proved that instead of the square of Euclidean norm 2.2.8, we can use any continuous function $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ to construct finite-sample exact confidence region. Therefore, in one dimension, we call the original SPS method quadratic SPS, since it uses $f(x) = x^2$. In addition, we introduce linear SPS for the case when $f(x) = x$ (i.e. f is identity). We always think of quadratic SPS if it is not stated otherwise.

For the sake of a small example we plotted the SPS confidence region and its defining parabolas, which are shown in Figure 3.1. In this case, we used Gaussian noise ($n = 3$) and chose $m = 4, q = 1$ parameters. All in all, we obtained three different perturbed parabolas. Each provides one intersection to the left of the LSE and one to right. The perturbed parabolas stay above the reference parabola in a bounded set (the visualization was inspired by [7], an introductory paper on certified system identification).

Two-sided confidence interval with quadratic SPS

Figure 3.1: $m = 4, q = 1$

In order to emphasise the relevance of SPS method, we visualized and compared the sizes of different confidence sets including the SPS based one in Figure 3.2. We considered 3 different ways of constructing 0.95 level, two-sided confidence intervals

Algorithm 7 SPS method (1-dimensional)

1. Generate a permutation π on $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$ uniformly.
2. Generate $m(m-1)$ Rademacher variables $(\alpha_{i,t})_{i=1,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ independently.
3. Define the reference parabola $S_0(\theta)^2$ and the perturbed parabolas $S_i(\theta)^2$ for $i \in [m-1]$.
4. Construct the following sets:

$$\mathcal{I}_a = \{i \in [m-1] : S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2, \pi(i) > \pi(0)\},$$

$$\mathcal{L}_u = \{i \in [m-1] : S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 = 0, \pi(i) < \pi(0)\}.$$

$$\mathcal{I} = \{i \in [m-1] : S_i(\theta)^2 \equiv S_0(\theta)^2\}$$

If $|\mathcal{I}_a| \geq q$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}$. If $|\mathcal{L}_u| \geq m - q$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset$. Either way the algorithm terminates.

5. Define $R \doteq m - |\mathcal{I}_a|$. For $i \in [m-1] \setminus \mathcal{I}$ calculate intersection pairs $\{\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}\}$ (i.e. the solutions of $S_i(\theta)^2 = S_0(\theta)^2$, possibly $\theta_{i,1} = \theta_{i,2}$). Define $\mathcal{O} = \bigcup_{i \in [m-1] \setminus \mathcal{I}} \{\theta_{i,1}, \theta_{i,2}\}$ ($k \doteq |\mathcal{O}|$).
 6. Sort the elements of set \mathcal{O} : $-\infty < \theta_1 < \theta_2 < \dots < \theta_k < \infty$. Let $(k_j)_{j=1}^k$ be a sequence, where $k_j \doteq |\{i \in [m-1] \setminus \mathcal{I} : S_i(\theta_j)^2 = 0\}|$.
 7. Initialize $j \leftarrow 1$, $L \leftarrow \hat{\theta}_n$. While $\theta_j < \hat{\theta}_n$:
 - (a) $R \leftarrow R - k_j$.
 - (b) If $R \leq m - q$, then $L \leftarrow \theta_j$ and break the loop.
 - (c) $j \leftarrow j + 1$.
 8. Initialize $j \leftarrow k$, $E \leftarrow \hat{\theta}_n$. While $\theta_j > \hat{\theta}_n$:
 - (a) $R \leftarrow R - k_j$.
 - (b) If $R \leq m - q$, then $E \leftarrow \theta_j$ and break the loop.
 - (c) $j \leftarrow j - 1$.
 9. If $L = E = \hat{\theta}_n$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \{\hat{\theta}_n\}$. Otherwise calculate $R_0(L), R_0(E)$.
 - $\hat{\Theta}_n = (L, E)$ if $R_0(L), R_0(E) > m - q$.
 - $\hat{\Theta}_n = [L, E]$ if $R_0(L), R_0(E) \leq m - q$.
 - $\hat{\Theta}_n = [L, E)$ if $R_0(L) \leq m - q, R_0(E) > m - q$.
 - $\hat{\Theta}_n = (L, E]$ if $R_0(L) > m - q, R_0(E) \leq m - q$.
-

Figure 3.2: Size comparison of confidence intervals

for the mean of standard Gaussian samples. One of the methods relies on the exact knowledge of standard normal cumulative distribution function (CDF) Φ . The same confidence set is used in z -test [3]. Let $(X_t)_{t=1}^n$ be an i.i.d. standard normal sample. Then the $1 - \varepsilon$ level confidence set based on the CDF of standard normal distribution is $\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n X_t - \frac{z_\varepsilon}{\sqrt{n}}, \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n X_t + \frac{z_\varepsilon}{\sqrt{n}}\right)$, where $z_\varepsilon = \Phi^{-1}(1 - \frac{\varepsilon}{2})$. The second type of interval is the one we got from subgaussian assumption (1.46). We used it with $\sigma = 1$, which the best possible estimate for the subgaussian constant. In addition, we set $\delta = 0.05$ to achieve 0.95 confidence level. Both of the aforementioned cases provide intervals whose lengths do not depend on the sample realization only on the sample size. In the remaining case of SPS method based confidence set, we chose parameters $m = 100, q = 5$ to achieve the same confidence level as by the previously mentioned parametric solutions. The minimal sample size was set to be $n = 8$ in order to avoid infinite intervals in case of SPS method with high probability. For different sample sizes we generated 1000 instances from the SPS method based intervals and calculated their average size and variance. Recall that if we generate 1000 times the SPS confidence regions for $m = 100$, and $q = 5$, then the probability that one of them becomes \mathbb{R} is not negligible (see Figure 2.1). In Figure 3.2, we indicated the standard deviation of the lengths of SPS intervals with the pale green band. We also calculated lengths of the aforementioned two data independent confidence sets (standard normal CDF and subgaussian assumption based confidence intervals) for the indicated sample sizes.

As the evaluation of the results, if one manages to avoid infinite SPS regions, then the length of SPS based confidence interval closely approximates the length of the normal CDF based intervals as the sample size grows. Moreover, in terms of confidence

region volume, SPS performs better than, in average, the subgaussian confidence set construction method, which suggests that using SPS intervals one may achieve sublinear regret in multi-armed bandit problems.

3.1.4 The linear SPS method

We have already mentioned the concept of linear SPS in Remark 3.1.5. The quadratic SPS method provides two-sided confidence intervals for θ^* . However, we intend to use these intervals in an upper confidence bound policy applied to multi-armed bandit problems, thus we would rather have a one-sided, semi-infinite set construction. Although we could take the upper bound E of $\hat{\Theta}_n$ and use $(-\infty, E]$ as an at least $1 - q/m$ level confidence set, but we would lose the exact confidence probability of the confidence regions. This justifies the need for the concept of linear SPS, which is a one-sided confidence interval construction.

Define the reference line and the perturbed lines for $i \in [m - 1]$ as follows:

$$S_0(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \theta) = \hat{\theta}_n - \theta \quad (3.27)$$

$$S_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} (Y_t - \theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t - \theta \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \right) \quad (3.28)$$

Observe that the slope of the reference line is always negative, as well as the absolute value of the slope of a perturbed line (which is between -1 and 1) cannot exceed the slope of $S_0(\theta)$.

Similarly as in the 1-dimensional quadratic SPS case we intend to analyze $\{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : S_0(\theta) \prec_{\pi} S_i(\theta)\}$ sets ($i \in [m - 1]$) which will build up the linear SPS confidence regions. Consider the root of $S_0(\theta) - S_i(\theta)$ function (i.e. the intersections the reference and a perturbed parabola).

$$S_0(\theta) = S_i(\theta) \iff \theta \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} \right) - \left(\hat{\theta}_n - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} Y_t \right) = 0 \quad (3.29)$$

Thus, either $\sum_{t=1}^n \alpha_{i,t} = 1$ and $S_0(\theta) \equiv S_i(\theta)$ or there is one intersection:

$$\theta_{i,1} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (1 - \alpha_{i,t}) Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^n (1 - \alpha_{i,t})} \quad (3.30)$$

Notice that if none of the perturbed lines are equivalent to the reference line, then for all $\theta > \max_{i \in [m-1]} \theta_{i,1}$ we have $S_0(\theta) < S_i(\theta)$ for every $i \in [m-1]$. Consequently, if we define a linear SPS based confidence region using $S_i(\theta)$ instead of $S_i(\theta)^2$ ($i \in \{0, \dots, m - 1\}$), then it becomes semi-infinite (assuming that it is not empty neither the whole space \mathbb{R}). However, it takes the form (c, ∞) for some real constant c , hence it is infinite in the

”wrong direction” from our point of view, because we intend to get an upper confidence bound type set. This problem can be resolved if we define the linear SPS confidence regions (i.e. intervals) in the following way:

$$\hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}} \doteq \bigcup_{\substack{\mathcal{I} \subseteq [m-1] \\ |\mathcal{I}|=q}} \bigcap_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \{\theta \in \mathbb{R} : S_i(\theta) \prec_{\pi} S_0(\theta)\}. \quad (3.31)$$

Namely, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ is the the confidence set if $S_0(\theta)$ is greater than at least q perturbed values in θ , according to \prec_{π} . In other words, $\theta \in \hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}}$ if $R_0^{\text{lin}}(\theta) > q$, where $R_0^{\text{lin}}(\theta)$ is the rank of $S_0(\theta)$ in the ascending order of $\{S_i(\theta)\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ (i.e. after sorting $\{S_i(\theta)\}_{i=0}^{m-1}$ according to \prec_{π} , $R_0^{\text{lin}}(\theta) = 1$ if $S_0(\theta)$ is the smallest, $R_0^{\text{lin}}(\theta) = 2$ if $S_0(\theta)$ is the second smallest, and so on). $S_0(\theta)$ has negative slope, which is less than or equal to the slope of any other perturbed line, thus $\hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}}$ will surely be an upper confidence bound type interval. Notice that linear SPS fits into the generalized SPS model presented in section 2.2.4. Consequently,

$$\mathbb{P}(\theta^* \in \hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}}) = 1 - \frac{q}{m}. \quad (3.32)$$

The linear SPS confidence region $\hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}}$ can be determined similarly as the quadratic SPS based confidence set $\hat{\Theta}_n$ (see Algorithm 7). The exact procedure is encapsulated in Algorithm 8. Just as in case of quadratic SPS, empty or two-sided infinite intervals may arise. However, either phenomenon occurs only if $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \mathbf{1}$. Unlike the quadratic case, here $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = -\mathbf{1}$ sequence is not problematic, and the corresponding perturbed line intersects $S_0(\theta)$ in the least-squares estimate $\hat{\theta}_n$. If $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n \neq \pm \mathbf{1}$, then $S_i(\theta) < S_0(\theta)$ in a semi-infinite interval (same applies to the case of $S_i(\theta) > S_0(\theta)$). In the algorithm, we defined R as a variable that stores the rank of $S_0(\theta)$ in a certain interval, which is initialized as $R \doteq 1 + |\mathcal{I}_u|$, since the rank is at least one plus the number of perturbed lines that are ”under” $S_0(\theta)$ for every $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$. Consider that up until the ”while loop” in the algorithm, we have already covered every case that could make $\hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}}$ empty or two-sided infinite. Consequently, if we reach θ_1 in the loop, then it will be the very intersection that defines the confidence set (the condition inside the loop in point (b) is never satisfied, thus E remains θ_1).

See Figure 3.3 as an example of linear SPS confidence interval. In this particular case, we chose $m = 8, q = 1$, and there were no perturbed lines identical to the reference line. It also illustrates that if we choose a larger q , i.e. we decrease confidence level, then it will lower the upper end of the interval.

Finally, we briefly outline the connection between linear and quadratic SPS. Consider a fixed sample $(Y_t)_{t=1}^n$. In case of linear SPS, every different sign sequence $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ provides a unique line, hence from n -element sample at most $2^n - 1$ unique perturbed lines can be made that are different from the reference line. On the other hand, $\frac{2^n}{2} - 1$ different perturbed parabolas can be made, since $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ and $-(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ provide the

Algorithm 8 linear SPS method

1. Generate a permutation π on $\{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$ uniformly.
2. Generate $m(m-1)$ Rademacher variables $(\alpha_{i,t})_{i=1,t=1}^{m-1,n}$ independently.
3. Define the reference line $S_0(\theta)$ and the perturbed lines $S_i(\theta)$ for $i \in [m-1]$.
4. Construct the following sets:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{I}_a &= \{i \in [m-1] : S_i(\theta) \equiv S_0(\theta), \pi(i) > \pi(0)\}, \\ \mathcal{I}_u &= \{i \in [m-1] : S_i(\theta) \equiv S_0(\theta), \pi(i) < \pi(0)\}.\end{aligned}$$

If $|\mathcal{I}_u| \geq q$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \mathbb{R}$. If $|\mathcal{I}_a| \geq m - q$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n = \emptyset$. Either way the algorithm terminates.

5. Define $R \doteq 1 + |\mathcal{I}_u|$ and $\mathcal{I} \doteq \mathcal{I}_a \cup \mathcal{I}_u$. For $i \in [m-1] \setminus \mathcal{I}$ calculate intersection $\theta_{i,1}$ (i.e. the solution of $S_i(\theta) = S_0(\theta)$). Define $\mathcal{O} = \{\theta_{i,1} : i \in [m-1] \setminus \mathcal{I}\}$ ($k \doteq |\mathcal{O}|$).
 6. Sort the elements of set \mathcal{O} : $-\infty < \theta_1 < \theta_2 < \dots < \theta_k < \infty$. Let $(k_j)_{j=1}^k$ be a sequence, where $k_j \doteq |\{i \in [m-1] \setminus \mathcal{I} : S_i(\theta_j) = 0\}|$.
 7. Initialize $j \leftarrow k$, $E \leftarrow \theta_1$. While $\theta_j > \theta_1$:
 - (a) $R \leftarrow R + k_j$.
 - (b) If $R > q$, then $E \leftarrow \theta_j$ and break the loop.
 - (c) $j \leftarrow j - 1$.
 8. If $R_0^{\text{lin}}(E) > q$, then $\hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}} = (-\infty, E]$, otherwise $\hat{\Theta}_n^{\text{lin}} = (-\infty, E)$.
-

Figure 3.3: Linear SPS

same parabolas, and $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ gives the reference parabola. Furthermore, the $2^n - 1$ unique perturbed lines intersect the reference line in $2^n - 1$ different points. In addition, there are $2 \cdot \left(\frac{2^n}{2} - 1\right) = 2^n - 2$ different intersections between the $m - 1$ number of unique perturbed parabolas and the reference parabola if for every $i \in [m - 1]$ $S_i(\hat{\theta}_n)^2 \neq 0$ (we saw that in this case there is only one or infinitely many intersections, see Lemma 3.1.1 and 3.1.3). Notice that all possible $2^n - 2$ quadratic SPS intersections are linear SPS intersections as well, since $S_i(\theta)^2 = S_0(\theta)^2 \iff (S_i(\theta) = S_0(\theta) \text{ or } -S_i(\theta) = S_0(\theta))$. Thus there is only one intersection that can occur in case of linear SPS but cannot by quadratic SPS (considering only unique parabolas and lines). This intersection corresponds to the LSE. When $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = -\mathbf{1}$, then $S_0(\theta) = S_i(\theta) \iff \theta = \hat{\theta}_n$, but if $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = -\mathbf{1}$, then $S_0^2(\theta) \equiv S_i^2(\theta)$.

Figure 3.4: Connection between one-sided linear and quadratic SPS

To give a visual point of view, given a 2 element standard Gaussian sample, we constructed all the possible unique SPS parabolas and lines. They were created by using all the possible two long sign sequences. All in all, the maximum number of lines is 4, and the maximum number of parabolas is 2. Here, one of the parabola is degenerate in the way that it has become a line (more about this phenomenon can be read in section 3.1.1). By choosing Gaussian sample, we can avoid the event that the LSE is the root of a perturbed parabola, which means that a perturbed parabola intersects the reference parabola in two points.

3.2 Sign-perturbation based UCB algorithm

In this final part of the thesis, we present our sign-perturbed sums based approach for decision making in stochastic multi-armed bandit environments.

3.2.1 Perturbation based stochastic multi-armed bandit algorithm

The multi-armed bandit policy to be presented here is built upon the optimism in the face of uncertainty principle. Similarly as in case of the previously examined stochastic multi-armed bandit algorithms (see section 1.3), in each round $t = 1, 2, \dots$ we build a one-sided confidence set for each and every arms' unknown mean using linear SPS method, and an arm with the highest upper bound is chosen in the given round (except when we require more data to achieve a prescribed probability).

In order to avoid infinite and empty SPS confidence region we rely on the following conjecture when we construct our new nonparametric bandit algorithm:

Conjecture 3.2.1. *The exact confidence bound $1 - \frac{\alpha}{m}$ holds for linear and quadratic SPS even if the n long sign sequences $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n$ are sampled without replacement for $i \in [m - 1]$, where m is at most 2^n in case of n -element sample $(Y_t)_{t=1}^n$.*

Consider what sampling sign sequences without replacement means. The sign sequence corresponding to the reference value is fixed, i.e. $(\alpha_{0,1}, \dots, \alpha_{0,n}) = \mathbf{1}$. The next sign sequence $(\alpha_{1,1}, \dots, \alpha_{1,n})$ is sampled from the set of all possible n long sign sequences except the constant one sequence $\mathbf{1}$. If $(\alpha_{1,1}, \dots, \alpha_{1,n}) = s_{1,1}, \dots, s_{1,n} \in \{-1, 1\}$, then the third sign sequence $(\alpha_{2,1}, \dots, \alpha_{2,n})$ cannot be $\mathbf{1}$ or $s_{1,1}, \dots, s_{1,n} \in \{-1, 1\}$, thus sampled from the remaining $2^n - 2$ possible sign sequences uniformly, and so on. Consequently, we can avoid degenerate confidence regions using this sign sampling approach with linear SPS, since difference sign sequences result in different lines. In case of quadratic SPS, we can still have problems due to the fact that the sequences $(\alpha_{i,t})_{t=1}^n = \pm \mathbf{1}$ give only one unique parabola. From a practical point of view, this special sign sampling has another benefit. Namely, when we work with smaller sample sizes random sign sampling often produces the same perturbed lines or parabolas (not necessary equivalent ones to the reference line or parabola), which means that we cannot exploit all the information that the data contains, unlike in case of sign sequence sampling without replacement, where we construct only unique perturbed lines (and perturbed parabolas are more likely to be unique).

The linear SPS based UCB algorithm can be seen in Algorithm 8. This is an anytime procedure, i.e. it does not depend on the horizon. $\hat{\Theta}_{n_a, a}^{lin}$ denotes the one-sided linear SPS interval that corresponds to arm a made by n_a -element sample. If there are enough samples from each arm, then the confidence level in round t is set to be $1 - \frac{1}{\lceil 1+t \log^2(t) \rceil}$,

Algorithm 9 Linear SPS based UCB

Input: action set $\mathcal{A} = [k]$.

1. For $t = 1, 2, \dots, k$ choose $A_t = t$ action.
 2. Set $q = 1$, define $m(t) = \lceil 1 + t \log^2(t) \rceil$, and initialize counters $n_j = 1$ for $j \in [k]$ (n_j stores the number of times arm j was chosen).
 3. For $t = k + 1, k + 2, \dots$
 - (a) If there is an action a such that $2^{n_a} < m(t)$ (when there is more than one, choose one randomly), then play $A_t = a$, and $n_a \leftarrow n_a + 1$.
 - (b) Otherwise, for $a = 1, \dots, k$:
 - i. Sample sign sequences without replacement, and construct $1 - q/m(t)$ level linear SPS confidence interval from the n_a element reward sample corresponding to arm a . Denote the interval by $\hat{\Theta}_{n_a, a}^{lin}$.
 - ii. Define $\text{UCB}_a = \sup \hat{\Theta}_{n_a, a}^{lin}$.
 - (c) Subsequently play $A_t = \operatorname{argmax}_{a \in [k]} \text{UCB}_a$, and $n_{A_t} \leftarrow n_{A_t} + 1$.
-

which is a rational approximation of the confidence level of asymptotically optimal UCB. The purpose of this particular choice is to be able to make fair comparison. Notice that we can make exponentially many perturbed lines: if there are n_j samples from arm j then $2^{n_j} - 1$ different $S_i(\theta)$ instances can be constructed. Since $\hat{\Theta}_{n_a, a}^{lin}$ can be a right-open interval, the upper confidence bound is defined as a supremum.

3.2.2 Regret comparative experiments

In terms of algorithm performance comparison, in this section when we talk about regret we refer to the pseudo regret instead (for the original regret definition see 1.1.6), which is defined as

$$\hat{R}_n(\pi, \nu) = n\mu^* - \sum_{t=1}^n \mu_{A_t}, \quad (3.33)$$

where μ^* is the mean of the optimal arm, and μ_{A_t} is the expected value of the arm that was chosen at time t according to the given policy. Notice that during analysis of SPS we never assumed that the expectation of the noise sequence exists (e.g. the variables $(N_t)_{t=1}^n$ could even follow Cauchy distribution). However, if we intend to measure the performance of the data perturbation based UCB algorithm, then the existence of expectation is also required. The advantage of pseudo regret is that one can measure bandit algorithm performance in a simulation while filtering out the observation noise $X_t - \mu_{A_t}$ [15].

We conducted numerical experiments using the Python programming language. We

distinguished three setups to compare our nonparametric linear SPS based UCB multi-armed bandit algorithm (see Algorithm 9) with the asymptotically optimal UCB policy (see Algorithm 2). We considered normal bandits (with unit variance) in all three cases, since Gaussian distribution has the heaviest tail probability for which Asymptotically optimal UCB guarantees that the upper bounds it provides for each arm are indeed upper bounds with probability at least $1 - \frac{1}{1+t \log^2(t)}$. We measured the pseudo regret of the MAB algorithms over 1000 rounds, and repeated the experiments 1000 times to calculate an average performance. We also assumed that the parameters of asymptotically optimal UCB are set perfectly, i.e. the exact value of every arm’s subgaussian constant is known. In this particular unit variance normal distribution case, the best possible estimate for the subgaussian constant is 1. The results are reported in Figure 3.5 and 3.6.

In case of two-armed bandits (see 3.5), and considering quite small, 0.2 suboptimality-gap (Figure 3.5b), the SPS based UCB and the asymptotically optimal UCB perform approximately the same in early stages ($n < 300$). As more and more rounds pass in the sequential decision making, the cumulative regret of SPS based UCB becomes the lower. Similar analysis can be given for larger, 0.5 suboptimality gap, but the point when SPS based UCB overcomes the asymptotically optimal UCB happens in a later stage. As one can see, SPS based UCB performs significantly worse in the early rounds. This can be explained by that the perturbation based policy tends to choose arms that have a shortage on samples (i.e. which are rarely played) to maintain high confidence level, thus it explores more in the early stages. In contrast to this, the asymptotically optimal UCB can increase confidence level without new sample, which is a clear advantage of a parametric approach. However, in real life applications the subgaussian constant is not given in advance, and the decision maker has to estimate it. In the 5-armed bandit case, we chose random suboptimality gaps from the interval $(0.25, 0.75)$ (new random choices in each of the 1000 repetitions). We experienced that the more arms there are the worse linear SPS based UCB performs compared to asymptotically optimal UCB. This phenomena can be explained by similar argument as in case of large suboptimality gaps.

Finally, we conclude the thesis by considering the benefits and pitfalls of the two algorithms we examined in these numerical experiments. In real life applications the subgaussian constants must be estimated for asymptotically optimal UCB. In case of normal sample, it can be done by estimating the variance of the distribution. On the other hand, SPS method does not require the existence of moments. Also note that subgaussian UCB policies cannot guarantee the inclusion of the unknown mean for distributions with heavy tails, and they rely on parametric assumption, i.e. subgaussianity. Furthermore, the perturbation based UCB relies only on symmetry assumption. Both the advantage and the disadvantage of linear SPS based UCB is the

Figure 3.5: 2-armed Gaussian bandits regret comparison

Figure 3.6: 5-armed Gaussian bandit

fact that it is a data-driven algorithm. It requires only mild statistical assumptions, and it is distribution-free, but to achieve high confidence level, extensive exploration of suboptimal arms (that may have high suboptimality gaps) is needed.

Summary

The aim of the thesis was to contribute to the vast theory of Sign-perturbed Sums (SPS) method and to analyze the possible applicability of SPS confidence regions in stochastic multi-armed bandit problems.

In the first chapter, we reviewed the concept of a reinforcement learning task called stochastic multi-armed bandit problem. We got acquainted with the notion of regret, which is the deficit that the decision-maker experiences due to suboptimal action. The goal of the decision maker is to minimize regret, which can be done by using Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) type policies. After reviewing useful concentration inequalities, two well-known UCB policies were presented: the historically relevant UCB1, and the asymptotically optimal UCB.

After that, we thoroughly examined the Sign-Perturbed Sums method, which is a distribution-free, non-asymptotic, finite sample confidence region construction algorithm that can be used to build exact confidence sets for the unknown parameter of linear regression models. The main assumption of the procedure is that the noises in the linear model are independent and symmetric about the origin. We reviewed many known properties of the SPS method, e.g. star convexity, strong consistency. In addition, we gave lower bounds for the probability of the events that the SPS confidence region is empty or becomes the whole space. The lower estimates showed that for small sample sizes and relatively high confidence level the probability of these events are not negligible. In a later part of the thesis, we also proved that these lower bounds are upper bounds as well in case of one-dimensional SPS (in case of empty regions, continuous noise is also required). In the final part of the second chapter, we considered several modifications of the SPS method. We proved that the exact, user-chosen confidence level holds not only when sign-perturbation is applied but even if the perturbation variables are symmetric about zero (and they take the value 0 with probability 0).

In general, the construction of SPS confidence sets is computationally demanding, thus they are typically approximated. In the third, final chapter of the thesis, we analyzed the one-dimensional SPS confidence regions, which are intervals. In that case, the confidence sets can be calculated in closed form. We presented an algorithm that determines these intervals. Furthermore, we introduced the concept of linear SPS, which provides semi-infinite intervals as confidence regions. For the sake of deeper understanding, we visualized the construction of the examined one-dimensional SPS methods. Using linear SPS, we proposed a new UCB policy for symmetric MAB environments. At the end of the thesis, we intended to empirically compare our algorithm to the previously reviewed asymptotically optimal UCB. After conducting numerical experiments using the Python programming language, we concluded that our proposed linear SPS based UCB algorithm performs efficiently in terms of regret, especially in harder tasks, i.e. when the suboptimality gaps are small.

As possible continuation of the research, the proof of the conjecture which our nonparametric bandit algorithm relies on is still a problem to be solved. Thereafter, the theoretical analysis of linear SPS based UCB could be performed. Namely, proving that its regret is sublinear in symmetric environment classes.

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